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Technical collaboration report with other European Partnerships and relevant initiatives

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Deliverable Abstract

This deliverable is a report on the technical collaboration of the EOSC Partnership with other European Partnerships and relevant initiatives. This second report focuses on the collaboration with European Partnerships as well as the collaboration with Common European Data Spaces. The objective of this deliverable is to report on the actions and opportunities for mutual collaboration and cooperation in line with the objectives of the EOSC Partnership’s Memorandum of Understanding.

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TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Definition
6GSNS	Joint Undertaking Smart Networks & Services
AC	EU Associated Countries
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AWP	Annual Work Programmes
CEDS	Common European Data Spaces
Chips JU	Chips Joint Undertaking
cPPP	Contractual Public-Private-Partnerships under Horizon 2020.
CSAs	Coordination and Support Actions
DOIs	Digital Object Identifiers
DPV	Data Privacy Vocabulary
DPVCG	Data Privacy Vocabulary and Controls Community Group
DS	Data Space
DSS2024	Data Spaces Symposium 2024
DSSC	Data Spaces Support Centre
EBDVF2023	European Big Data Value Forum
EC	European Commission
EGD	European Green Deal
EHDS	European Health Data Space
EIT-KICs	EIT Knowledge and Innovation Communities
EJP	European Joint Programme
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC GA	EOSC General Assembly
EOSC-A	EOSC Association
ERA	European Research Area
EU	European Union
EuroHPC	European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking

FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse
FP	Framework Programme
GA	General Assembly
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HE	Horizon Europe
HPC	High Performance Computing
IAM4EU	Innovative Materials for Europe
INFRAG	Infrastructure Advisory Group
JTIs	Joint technology initiatives
JU	Joint Undertaking
JUs	Joint Undertakings
LDS	Language Data Space
MAR	Multi-annual Roadmap
MFF	Multiannual Financial Framework
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
MS	EU Member States
OS	Open Science
PIDs	Persistent Identifiers
PKH	Partnership Knowledge Hub
PMs	Person Months
PPPs	Public-Private Partnerships
R&I	Research & Innovation
RIAG	Research and Innovation Advisory Group
RIAs	Research and Innovation Actions
RTD	Research, technological development and demonstration
SAML	Security Assertion Markup Language
SIMPL	Smart Middleware Platform
SOC	Security Operation Centre
SRIAs	Strategic Research and Innovation Agendas
TFEU	Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union
TRE	Trusted Research Environments
WP	Work Programme

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Executive Summary

This report is the second and final deliverable describing the efforts of EOSC Focus T3.3 to liaise with European Partnerships and other relevant initiatives such as Common European Data Spaces (CEDS)¹. The activities conducted contribute towards Strategic Pillar 4 “Linking with other Common European Data Spaces and beyond” of the EOSC Multi-Annual Roadmap (MAR) 2026-2027.

The three different forms of European Partnerships possible under Horizon Europe - co-funded, institutionalised and co-programmed - were analysed in detail by three assessments, included as Appendices 2, 3 and 4, which were provided to the EOSC Association Board of Directors during 2024 as input towards the ongoing consideration of the possible legal form and governance of EOSC post-2027. Complementary work took place in WP5 which focussed more specifically on financial aspects of European Partnerships.

The work served to increase the knowledge and understanding within EOSC Focus and the EOSC Association of the range of topics, objectives and types of European Partnerships under Horizon Europe. It identified those Partnerships likely to have relevance to EOSC, and it helped to inform lines of enquiry to pursue in bilateral contacts with selected Partnerships. In addition, interactions and collaborations took place with Partnerships and related groups of interest such as ERA4Health, Metrology, PRIMA, IAM4EU and the HE Partnership Knowledge Hub, motivated in part by the commitments of the Memorandum of Understanding of the EOSC Partnership. These contacts increased understanding of Partnerships and fostered cooperation.

The three documents were built upon further in analyses of the funding aspects of Institutionalised European Partnerships, including a study of the EuroHPC Joint Undertaking, carried out in the context of EOSC Focus WP5 and reported in deliverable D5.2.

Contributing further to Strategic Pillar 4, *Linking with other Common European Data Spaces and beyond*, of the EOSC MAR 2026-2027, EOSC Focus explored connections, culminating in organising a workshop in December 2024 to exchange knowledge and experience with selected INFRAEOSC projects, and to seek potential synergies between EOSC and several other Common European Data Spaces and with the DSSC (Data Spaces Support Centre). Four Common European Data Spaces took part in the workshop: Cultural Heritage, Green Deal, Health, and Language. Projects which participated in the workshop, as well as EOSC Focus, were Titan, FAIR Impact, Blue Cloud 2026, EOSC Beyond and RAISE. The workshop fostered dialogue, identified opportunities for alignment, and set the stage for future collaborative efforts which should be built upon in future.

Future collaborations, both with Partnerships and Data Spaces, could build on the work done in EOSC Focus, whether in the EOSC Association Advisory Group on Data Spaces, or in EOSC Gravity or another project. Collaboration activities could deliver mutual benefits in terms of increased impact and tackling common challenges, or developing compatible solutions and achieving efficiencies, and may also provide further valuable input towards the ongoing consideration of the post-2027 governance and funding of EOSC.

¹ Note that EOSC is defined as the cross-cutting Research and Innovation Data Space. See the DG RTD statement *EOSC, the transverse European data space for science, research and innovation*, December 2022, at <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/61134f17-7f50-11e4-9887-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

1 Introduction

D3.3 was elaborated in the frame of the [EOSC Focus project](#) (June 2022-May 2025). It covers the work conducted in WP3 of the project during the period December 2023-December 2024, describing the work done and the collaboration with other European Partnerships and other Common European Data Spaces, in line with the [expected supporting activities](#) as expressed in the Horizon Europe call for projects under which the EOSC Focus project was funded to “effectively cooperate and establish links with other selected Horizon Europe Partnerships as well as with other relevant initiatives, including sectoral data spaces”.

Everybody who follows EOSC knows that it is going through a rapid evolution, as is the landscape in which it operates. The more theoretical work from the early stages of the EOSC Partnership is now beginning to manifest itself in a concrete way. EOSC is entering its operational phase with the launch of the first node of the EOSC Federation, the [EOSC EU node](#) (officially launched at the [EOSC Symposium](#) in Berlin on 22 October 2024). Discussions and analyses to find a suitable governance model for EOSC post-27 in line with these developments have already started. The EOSC Focus project executed different analyses on Partnerships/models to support the EOSC Partnership in this exploration (see chapter 2).

In parallel with the rapid evolution of EOSC, it became desirable to review the existing and planned collaborations with other European Partnerships, and to perform a thorough analysis of the European Partnerships to decide which (additional) Partnerships might be beneficial to reach out to. The collaborations with current European Partnerships are also described in chapter 2.

Additionally, a workshop was organised with the initial goal to facilitate concertation between European Partnerships, Common European Data Spaces [R7] and INFRAEOSC projects whose work is related to European Partnerships (other than EOSC) and Data Spaces. To identify the relevant projects and the European Partnerships and Data Spaces that are connected to these projects, a questionnaire was sent out to the INFRAEOSC projects active in the second half of 2024 (see [Appendix 1](#)). The responses obtained show that 5 INFRAEOSC projects are doing work related to Data Spaces, but no project has connections to other European Partnerships apart from EOSC. In the end, the workshop brought together representatives from several Data Spaces, the DSSC (Data Spaces Support Center), and INFRAEOSC projects. The workshop and its results are described in chapter 3, and show evidence of the need for close collaboration on specific topics.

Chapter 4 closes this report with reflections and perspectives for future collaborations.

2 HE Partnerships

2.1 Introduction

During the second half of the EOSC Focus project, the activities of Task 3.3, *Liaise with European Partnerships and other relevant initiatives*, focused on European Partnerships and their significance in advancing Horizon Europe's objectives, and on the broader framework of the European Research Area (ERA). The European Partnerships are a key mechanism for structuring the ERA, contributing directly to the EU's strategic Research and Innovation priorities, sustainability of projects, sustainable development, digital transformation, and health research. By addressing common challenges, leveraging investments beyond the scope of individual countries, and minimising duplication of research efforts, the European Partnerships enhance the effectiveness and impact of Research & Innovation funding, driving systemic transitions aligned with EU priorities. The European Partnerships offer a structured platform for collaboration, fostering long-term synergies across value chains and ecosystems through Strategic Research and Innovation Agendas (SRIAs). During 2024, three individual assessments on the European Partnerships and their governance were produced for the EOSC Association to support the evaluation and discussion on the development of the EOSC and its governance model post-2027. These efforts were complemented by interactions with relevant partnerships such as ERA4Health, Metrology, and PRIMA facilitating closer collaboration and furthering the strategic role of EOSC. These activities are described in the sections below.

2.2 Input to Consideration of EOSC Governance and Operational Models

The implementation of EOSC is based on a long-term process² of alignment and coordination pursued by the European Commission since 2015. This has involved a diverse range of stakeholders across the European research landscape. It also requires adjustments to the strategy and governance model as it evolves. The current implementation phase (2021-2030) is taking place in the context of the Co-Programmed European Partnership for EOSC³, which marks a significant development in its governance structure. This partnership, which operates within the Horizon Europe framework programme (2021-2027), is instrumental in driving the implementation of EOSC and will continue until 2030. The collaboration between the EOSC Association and the European Commission forms the foundation for advancing open science, uptake of FAIR principles, and the integration of research infrastructures across Europe.

The EOSC Association and the European Commission have engaged in a process to define the EOSC evolution and operations post-2027, including considerations around governance, funding and the future of the EOSC Partnership. This process involved key stakeholders from the EOSC Co-programmed Partnership, comprising the European Commission, the EOSC Association, as well as the EU Member States and Associated Countries represented in the EOSC Steering Board. Within the EOSC Association, both members and observers were involved in the process. As part of this initiative, T3.3 contributed to the discussion by elaborating three individual assessments for the EOSC Association. These documents provide essential information/insights to facilitate the ongoing

² <https://eosc.eu/eosc-about/>

³ <https://eosc.eu/partnership>

discussion about the development of EOSC governance and operational models, serving as crucial resources for shaping its future.

The first piece of work, titled *Overview European Partnerships under Horizon Europe (HE)*, is an 18-page report that provides a detailed analysis of the three types of European Partnership established under Horizon Europe. It provides a comprehensive summary of each partnership type, including their legal structures, funding models, and research focus, with particular emphasis on Institutionalised European Partnerships under Articles 185 and 187 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU). This document serves as a key reference for understanding the role of European Partnerships in shaping the European Research Area and advancing EU policy objectives (see [Appendix 2](#)).

The *Analysis of specific Joint Undertakings (JUs) under Article 187 TFEU* focuses on three JUs, "Chips," "EuroHPC," and "Smart Networks and Services". These initiatives address critical areas such as semiconductors, smart networks and services, and high-performance computing respectively, which are particularly relevant to EOSC. The analysis evaluates the pros and cons of adopting the JU model for EOSC, considering the benefits and risks at multiple levels. These include global concerns such as the dilution of open science principles, institutional challenges, including governance misalignment; and obstacles within the research community, such as barriers to innovation. This second document contributes to the ongoing dialogue on the governance and operational models for EOSC's future (see [Appendix 3](#)).

Finally, the report *Analysis/exploration of the thematic partnerships under Horizon Europe* examines 49 thematic partnerships, identifying potential opportunities for collaboration with EOSC. A detailed spreadsheet was created to map these opportunities, highlighting potential interactions that could reinforce the EOSC's implementation and enhance its integration with existing research domains. The document is also instrumental in understanding how EOSC can position itself as an advanced and cross-cutting Data Space, strengthening its connections with different research areas across Europe (see [Appendix 4](#)).

These three documents were built upon further by EOSC Focus in its work examining the financial models of Institutionalised European Partnerships under Arts 185 and 187 TFEU, including the EuroHPC Joint Undertaking. This is reported in deliverable D5.2.

2.3 Contacts between EOSC and other European Partnerships

Collaborations between EOSC and other initiatives are important not only because they are a requirement of the MoU, and to examine their governance, but also to avoid duplication of work and to learn from each other. So far, EOSC has had contact with ERA4Health, Metrology, PRIMA and IAM4EU and is furthermore active in the HE Partnership Knowledge Hub. The EOSC Focus team is supporting these contacts by providing information about EOSC requested by the other Partnerships, and by maintaining some of the contacts themselves. The current and past collaborations are explained here below more in detail:

ERA4Health

For EOSC, the ERA4Health Partnership is a useful platform to exchange experience about the challenges (organisational, governance, collaborations) many partnerships are facing. ERA4Health

has set up an active stakeholder group, called “Synergies Working group”. The European Partnerships which participate in the regular workshops and events, such as a. o. the EOSC partnership, are of interest for ERA4Health either content- or governance-wise.

Metrology

The Metrology Partnership, managed by Euramet, is already mentioned in the EOSC Partnership Memorandum of Understanding [R1]. Since the EOSC Partnership is exploring the options for future governance after 2027, Metrology is an interesting partnership for EOSC to learn from, since it is one of the few examples of partnerships under Art. 185. EOSC and Metrology had several contacts, discussing the pros and cons of an Art. 185 partnership, the last one taking place before the EOSC-A General Assembly #8 in May 2024 to prepare the GA session “Considerations for an Institutional Partnership based on Art. 185 TFEU”.

PRIMA

To better understand the requirements of establishing and running an Institutionalised Partnership under Art. 185, EOSC also reached out to the Partnership for Research and Innovation in the Mediterranean Area (PRIMA) which is an Art. 185 Partnership. The collaboration with PRIMA resulted in a presentation by the Director of the PRIMA Partnership Secretariat, Octavi Quintana Trias, during the EOSC-A GA #8 session “Considerations for an Institutional Partnership based on Art. 185 TFEU”. The [information presented](#) provided in-depth information for all EOSC-A members.

IAM4EU

The Partnership on [Innovative Materials for Europe](#) (IAM4EU) is a Co-programmed Partnership, launched by the European Commission under the Horizon Europe work programme 2025-2027. In order to prepare for the IAM4EU partnership (at the time of the collaboration, IAM4EU was still in the preparation phase and not yet established), and to get an overall picture of the potential for collaboration with other partnerships, EOSC and IAM4EU had several detailed discussions in 2024 on the goals and approaches of both partnerships. However, since IAM4EU will start only in 2025, the collaboration is currently on-hold.

Horizon Europe Commission Expert Group on [Partnership Knowledge Hub](#) (PKH)

“The group’s mission is to advise the Commission in the implementation of the strategic coordinating process for EU R&I partnerships, and to provide a forum for coordination and cooperation with Member States and related stakeholders.”⁴ The Expert Group’s goal is to maximise the impact of (joint) investments made through European Partnerships.

The EOSC Partnership understands the importance of collaboration between European Partnerships and therefore plays an active role in the PKH, supported by EOSC Focus, by attending the PKH meetings, providing relevant information about EOSC to the PKH members, and contributing actively to its joint documents & surveys as well as to the PKH workshops. During the last [European Partnership Stakeholder Forum on 4 and 5 December 2024](#), the Secretary General of the EOSC Association and Project Coordinator of EOSC Focus, Ute Gunsenheimer, joined the panel discussion about “20 years of European Partnerships - reflections and achievements”.

⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/expert-groups-register/screen/expert-groups/consult?lang=en&groupId=3783&fromMeetings=true&meetingId=26959>

3 EOSC and the Common European Data Spaces

3.1 EOSC, the European Research and Innovation Data Space

EOSC is one of the Common European Data Spaces, as illustrated in the EC diagram in figure 1 below. It is considered to be the Common European Data Space for research and innovation (see footnote 1). EOSC Focus deliverable D3.1 ("Technical Collaboration with other European Partnerships and relevant initiatives - Focus on Common European Data Spaces"), published in March 2024, examines the concept, key features and design principles of Data Spaces (see [R5]). As also described in D3.1, EOSC continues to collaborate with the Data Space Support Centre (DSSC) - see [appendix 5](#) for more details. Now that EOSC is entering its operational phase with the launch of the [EOSC EU node](#), the first node of the [EOSC Federation](#), it becomes increasingly important for EOSC to collaborate more with the sectoral Data Spaces, to ensure that data is as widely interoperable as possible.

T3.3 wished to facilitate concertation between European Partnerships, Common European Data Spaces and relevant INFRAEOSC projects. As explained in chapter 1, a T3.3 survey of the INFRAEOSC projects (see Appendix 1) discovered, however, that none of the projects has connections to any of the European Partnerships except for EOSC. The concertation, in the form of a face-to-face workshop in Vienna in December 2024, therefore gathered representatives from several Data Spaces, the DSSC (Data Space Support Centre) and INFRAEOSC projects.

Figure 1 - Data Spaces landscape (source: slide from EC presentation “Simpl programme”, EUDAT conference, session “Latest from the Data Spaces”, December 2024⁵)

The Vienna workshop and its conclusions, building on and updating D3.1, are described in this chapter.

⁵ <https://www.eudat.eu/events/conferences/eudat-conference-2024/keeping-data-spaces-SIMPL>

3.2 Workshop on the collaboration between Data Spaces and the EOSC

Fostering connections between EOSC, other Data Spaces, and HE Partnerships is essential to shape a shared vision for the future and achieve strategic alignment, thus avoiding duplication of efforts and investments. Bridging gaps across various thematic and domain-specific agendas, promoting cross-fertilisation of activities, and identifying stakeholders' priorities are key to driving collaboration to unlock the full potential for synergies [R3].

In this context, EOSC Focus sought to deepen the understanding of areas of possible collaboration and alignment between selected Data Spaces and EOSC in their use of sectoral data. This exploratory phase engaged diverse stakeholders, including HE INFRAEOSC projects, Data Spaces, and other EOSC-related actors.

The process culminated in a hybrid workshop aimed at fostering dialogue, identifying opportunities for alignment, and setting the stage for future collaborative efforts.

There are a growing number of Common European Data Spaces (see [R7]). All may have the potential for cooperation with EOSC. Based on their maturity and estimated relevance for EOSC (availability of research data and existing collaborations with EOSC and INFRAEOSC projects), the following Data Spaces were invited to join the workshop on Data Spaces (see [Appendix 5](#) for a description of each of these Data Spaces and most recent evolutions): Common European Cultural Heritage, Common European Green Deal, Health (EHDS) and Language (LDS).

Based on the response to the questionnaire in which the projects indicated the activities on European Partnerships and Data Spaces (see also [Appendix 1](#)), the following INFRAEOSC projects were invited to join the workshop: EOSC TITAN, FAIR -Impact, Blue Cloud 2026, EOSC Beyond, RAISE, EOSC Focus (organiser). A description of each project, their connections with Data Spaces, and their relevance for EOSC are described in [Appendix 5](#). The setup of the workshop can be found in [Appendix 7](#).

Summary of synergies

The workshop enabled the identification of concrete areas of common interest, listed in detail in [Appendix 6](#), that can be further explored to ensure collaborative and complementary value creation between the Data Spaces and EOSC.

The area of **data sharing, protection, and security mechanisms** (see [table 1](#)), anchored in the need to accelerate the use of FAIR data in Data Spaces, must focus on achieving common progress in managing intellectual property, commercial, personal, confidential, and sensitive data. This should be achieved whilst also implementing advanced security solutions such as encryption, AI-driven cybersecurity, and interoperable identity management.

The area of **technical infrastructure, interoperability, and integration** (see [table 2](#)) identified several challenges that could be addressed jointly to avoid duplication and enhance effectiveness across Data Spaces. These include the use of persistent identifiers (PIDs) or Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) and the adoption of common policies and standards. The evolution towards the EOSC Federation will require a higher degree of integration and the adoption of guidelines to ensure interoperability – the "glue" that enables EOSC to function effectively.

The area of **AI application to support FAIR data and improve data quality** (see [table 3](#)) highlights the role that AI can play throughout the research lifecycle. By automating metadata enrichment, aligning data formats, and streamlining classification, AI facilitates seamless cross-disciplinary collaboration within EOSC. Additionally, empirical evidence (see [Appendix 6](#)) demonstrates that adopting FAIR principles brings substantial benefits, including reduced data processing efforts and cost savings. The benefits of AI in Data Spaces could be maximised by tackling these opportunities jointly, and together addressing related technical, legal and ethical issues.

Conclusions of the workshop

The findings of the workshop in [Appendix 6](#) indicate that EOSC and other Data Spaces face common challenges and opportunities, and that these have to be tackled from an early stage of Data Spaces' evolution. EOSC should cooperate more closely with non-research Data Spaces, clouds and infrastructures and build common knowledge, so there is mutual benefit between the Data Spaces/infrastructures: all face similar issues and need to build on common knowledge and even business value between Data Spaces. In the long run, the cost of establishing and maintaining parallel environments could cast a shadow over the exchange and reuse of data. Finding synergies between Data Spaces should be incorporated as an integral part of their evolutionary process model. The participants of the workshop indicated that they were very satisfied with the approach and the organisation of the workshop and that this was one of the first initiatives to bring the Data Spaces and the EOSC together. The DSSC asked to re-use the material for enriching the discussions on the Blueprint 2.0.

4 Reflections and perspectives for future collaborations

Analysis of the various forms of European Partnerships was an important exercise through which EOSC Focus WP3 gathered valuable information for the EOSC Association Board, to inform the ongoing process of defining the future legal form and governance model of EOSC. The analysis was supplemented by outreach to and interaction with several individual European Partnerships, helping to foster relationships, but also to learn about these Partnerships' experiences and gain a better understanding of the pros and cons of the different forms of European Partnership. It should be noted that the types of Partnerships available in FP10 may differ from those for Horizon Europe, and not all types of Horizon Europe Partnerships will necessarily be continued in future.

Several European Partnerships were still at an early stage of implementation, and not fully operational, when they were examined or contacted by EOSC Focus. T3.3 recommends that the initial fact-finding performed, and relationships established are further built on in future, to the mutual benefit of all, and it may be expected that more profound discussions will be possible as the Partnerships mature. This would contribute further towards maximising EOSC's and other Partnerships' respective impacts and helping to guide one another's strategic directions. The deliberation over the future governance and legal form of EOSC is expected to continue throughout 2025 and beyond; further discussion with other Partnerships during that time may deliver additional benefits for EOSC. It would be worthwhile for a future project (e.g. EOSC Gravity) to develop a strategy for interaction and a programme of joint activities with other Partnerships, for example to identify, develop and exploit common interests or mutual learning points. In the short term this may provide further input towards consideration of the future legal form and governance model of EOSC, but it may also create joint insights and shared positions, for example relating to the future forms of European Partnerships, or to ways in which Partnerships, working together, could achieve efficiencies or mutual assistance.

Whilst building mutual knowledge and understanding is important for European Partnerships, the workshop reported in section 3.2 and appendices 5-7 demonstrated clearly that it is also important for the Common European Data Spaces (CEDs). These are a key part of the EC's Strategy for Data, and EOSC, as the Research and Innovation Data Space, is currently one of the most developed of the CEDs. EOSC has the opportunity to foster relationships with the other CEDs to tackle common challenges and develop compatible (interoperable) solutions, potentially taking a leadership role where relevant and mutually beneficial. T3.3 recommends that the knowledge gathered by EOSC Focus about other Data Spaces and about relevant activities in INFRAEOSC projects, including the areas for possible cooperation identified by the workshop, should be used as a basis for further collaboration, whether in the EOSC-A Advisory Group on Data Spaces⁶, in EOSC Gravity, or in another future project.

⁶ Further information can be found in the meeting minutes of the EOSC-A GA #7, Item08 (see [R10])

References

No	Description/Link
R1	Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) EOSC Partnership https://eosc.eu/sites/default/files/20210215_EOSC_MoU_FinalDraft.pdf
R2	EOSC Strategic and Research Innovation Agenda SRIA 1.3 https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/12/20241031_SRIA_1.3_final_Annex.pdf
R3	Performance of European Partnerships - Biennial Monitoring Report 2022 on partnerships in Horizon Europe https://projects.research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/en/knowledge-publications-tools-and-data/interactive-reports/performance-european-partnerships-2022
R4	Performance of European Partnerships - Biennial Monitoring Report 2024 on partnerships in Horizon Europe https://www.era-learn.eu/documents/ec_rtd_rec-24-004_bmr_report3.pdf/@@download/file/ec_rtd_rec-24-004_bmr_report3.pdf
R5	EOSC Focus - D3.1 - EOSC Technical Collaboration with other European Partnerships and relevant initiatives https://zenodo.org/records/10893958
R6	Key concepts of Data Spaces, DSSC https://dssc.eu/space/bv15e/766061351/Introduction+-+Key+Concepts+of+Data+Spaces#1.-What-Is-a-Data-Space?
R7	Second staff working document on data spaces, 2024 https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/second-staff-working-document-data-spaces
R8	Cost-Benefit analysis for FAIR research data - Cost of not having FAIR research data, European Commission 2018 Cost-Benefit analysis for FAIR research data - Cost of not having FAIR research data
R9	FAIR principles to improve the impact on health research management outcomes, Martínez-García, Alicia et al., Heliyon, Volume 9, Issue 5, e15733, 2023 https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/37205991/
R10	Meeting minutes of the EOSC-A General assembly #7, November 2023 https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/01/7th-General-Assembly-November-2023-%E2%80%93-Minutes.pdf
R11	EOSC Focus deliverable D5.2 “Sustainability status and plans/issues for future work” Link to be added
R12	Council Regulation establishing the Joint Undertakings under Horizon Europe and repealing Regulations (EC) No 219/2007, (EU) No 557/2014, (EU) No 558/2014, (EU) No 559/2014, (EU) No 560/2014, (EU) No 561/2014 and (EU) No 642/2014 https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32021R2085
R13	Commission Staff Working Document. EU Missions two years on: An assessment of progress in shaping the future we want and reporting on the review of Mission Areas and areas for institutionalised partnerships based on Articles 185 and 187 TFEU. Brussels, 19.7.2023. SWD (2023) 260 final. COM (2023) 457 final https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52023SC0260&qid=1704984843316

R14	Annual report on EU Joint Undertakings for the financial year 2022 https://www.eca.europa.eu/ECAPublications/SAR-JUS-2022/RAS-Jus-FY2022_EN.pdf
R15	Proposal for a COUNCIL REGULATION establishing the Joint Undertakings under Horizon Europe COM/2021/87 final https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A52021PC0087
R16	Legal provisions of COM(2021) 87 - Joint Undertakings under Horizon Europe. November 19, 2021 https://www.eumonitor.eu/9353000/1/j4nvhd fcs8bljza_j9vvik7m1c3gyxp/vlgkodah31yz
R17	European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Impact assessment for institutionalised European partnerships under Horizon Europe, Publications Office of the European Union, 2020 https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/295096
R18	Draft proposal for a European Partnership under Horizon Europe European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Partnership. May 2020. https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2020-06/ec_rtd_he-partnership-open-science-cloud-eosc.pdf
R19	Consolidated Version of the Treaty Establishing the European Atomic Energy Community (2012/C 327/01). Source: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:12012A/TXT
R20	European Partnerships under Horizon Europe: results of the structured consultation of Member States. Year 2019 https://www.era-learn.eu/documents/final_report_ms_partnerships.pdf
R21	Provisions related to European Partnerships in the Horizon Europe Common Understanding, Era-Learn https://www.era-learn.eu/documents/provisions_horizoneurope
R22	Horizon 2020 budget and implementation. A guide to the structure of the programme. European Parliament. European Union. 2015 https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/IDAN/2015/571312/EPRS_IDA%282015%29571312_EN.pdf
R23	European Partnerships in Horizon Europe https://eufundingoverview.be/funding/european-partnerships-in-horizon-europe-under-horizon-europe
R24	Supporting the EOSC Partnership in further consolidating the coordination and sustainability of the EOSC ecosystem https://cordis.europa.eu/programme/id/HORIZON_HORIZON-INFRA-2024-EOSC-01-02
R25	The European Court of Auditors gives green light to Joint Undertakings https://era.gv.at/news-items/the-european-court-of-auditors-gives-green-light-to-joint-undertakings/
R26	European Partnerships in Horizon Europe https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/european-partnerships-horizon-europe_en#identifying-partnerships
R27	Joint Undertakings: analysis of collaboration mechanisms with European Structural and Investment Funds - ESIF in an Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) context: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/333210160_Joint_Undertakings_analysis_of_collaboration_mechanisms_with_ESI_Funds_in_an_S3_context

Appendix 1 - Questionnaire INFRAEOSC projects

Questionnaire on Common European Data Spaces and European Partnerships

With this questionnaire, we would like to get more information on the work that the INFRAEOSC projects are doing with regard to Common European Data Spaces and European Partnerships.

The project [EOSC Focus](#) works on both Data Spaces and European Partnerships. We already published a deliverable focussing on [Data Spaces](#). However, we feel that the Data Spaces are still in the process of being formed, and that most of the European Partnerships are working rather in silos, not knowing of the work in other Partnerships.

Our intention is to understand better the work that you are doing in the projects with regard to both topics, with the goal to learn from each other, finding synergies, interesting use cases for the EOSC and to get valuable insights for possible (future) collaborations.

Please provide your input to Friederike.Schroeder-Pander@belnet.be before 15 July 2024.

Thank you in advance for your contribution!

The EOSC Focus T3.3 team

Questionnaire

1. Do you have in your project one or more tasks which include work on [Data Spaces](#) (eg. Health, Language, Green Deal, Cultural Heritage,...)?

Yes/No

If yes:

- How many PMs are reserved for the work on Data Spaces?
- What are you doing or aim to do precisely with regard to Data Spaces?
- What further information about, or synergies or collaborations with Data Spaces, do you feel are relevant for EOSC?

2. Is your project collaborating with [European Partnerships](#) (eg. EuroHPC, Metrology, ADRA, Era for Health, Biodiversa+, Blue Economy...)?

Yes/No

If yes:

- Which are the European Partnerships you are collaborating with?
- What is the goal of the collaboration?
- Which kind of (joint) activities are you doing with these Partnerships?
- What other aspects or activities of other European Partnerships do you feel are relevant to EOSC? About which it may be relevant to gather information or establish collaborations?

If no:

- Do you plan to collaborate in the future with other European Partnerships? If yes, which are the Partnerships in focus and what is the goal of the planned collaboration?

What aspects or activities of European Partnerships do you feel are relevant to EOSC? About which it may be relevant to gather information or establish collaborations?

Appendix 2 - Overview European Partnerships under HE

A description realised in the frame of EOSC Focus project, January 2024

1. Introductory Statement

Within the scope of task **T3.3 Liaise with European Partnerships and other relevant initiatives** of the EOSC Focus project, this document aims to provide a consolidated view of European Partnerships with a major focus on the Joint Undertakings - JUs model that will illustrate the “foreground⁷” information that has been achieved and produced during the course of the EOSC Focus project by the partners. Conversely, it is understood that the further use and handling of this content/document by EOSC-A will produce “background” information. Background material, specially concerning legal matters, that would have formed part of the performer’s normal output regardless of project participation

In this section you will find general information on European Partnership in [Horizon Europe](#), as well as detailed information on the three partnership formats in Horizon Europe and more detail on JUs.

2. European Partnerships in Horizon Europe⁸

[European Partnerships](#) are initiatives in which the European Commission and private and/or public partners commit themselves to jointly support the development and implementation of a research and innovation program. They are a key implementation tool of Horizon Europe, and contribute significantly to achieving the EU’s political priorities, such as the Green Deal, Europe’s digital strategy or pandemic preparedness.

The strategic approach under Horizon Europe⁹ aims to improve the coherence of the partnerships among themselves and in interaction with other instruments in the Framework Programme. In addition, the partnerships are to be made more open and transparent in terms of participants, activities and results.

European R&I partnerships shall furthermore develop the European Research Area (ERA), overcome the fragmentation of the R&I landscape, avoid duplication with national or regional research activities and promote competitiveness and innovation.

A. Types of European Partnerships in Horizon Europe

The proposal for a regulation establishing Horizon Europe¹⁰ stipulates that parts of the Horizon Europe Framework Program can be implemented through European partnerships and the other part through traditional calls.

⁷ Foreground” is material that has originated after the inception of the project and has been undertaken solely because of the performer’s participation in the project.

⁸ The *Horizon Europe Regulation* (common understanding) that the European Partnerships are expected to adhere to the “principles of Union added value, transparency, openness, impact within and for Europe, strong leverage effect on sufficient scale, long-term commitments of all the involved parties, flexibility in implementation, coherence, coordination and complementarity with Union, local, regional, national and, where relevant, international initiatives or other partnerships and missions.” The provisions and criteria set out for the selection and implementation of the European Partnerships reflect these principles. Source: European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *Impact assessment for institutionalised European partnerships under Horizon Europe*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2020, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/295096>

⁹ The exact budget dedicated to European Partnerships under Horizon Europe will be agreed only upon decisions on the multiannual financial framework (MFF) 2021-2027 and the overall budget for Horizon Europe. In December 2017, the Council nevertheless introduced the principle of a “possible capping of partnership instruments in the FP budget”. Source: Council of the European Union (2017) From the Interim Evaluation of Horizon 2020 towards the ninth Framework Programme. Council conclusions 15320/17

¹⁰ Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council establishing Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, laying down its rules for participation and dissemination - Common understanding’, March 2019

The Horizon Europe proposal lays down the conditions and principles for establishing European Partnerships and distinguishes between 3 implementation modes: Co-funded European Partnerships, Co-programmed European Partnerships, and Institutionalised European Partnerships in accordance with Article 185 TFEU or Article 187 TFEU.

All European Partnerships will be designed in line with the new policy approach for more objective-driven and impactful partnerships. They are based on the common criteria in Annex III of the Horizon Europe Regulation¹¹, with few distinguishing elements for the different forms of implementation. All European Partnerships will be based on an agreed Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda/roadmap agreed among partners and with the Commission. For each of them the objectives, key performance and impact indicators, and outputs to be delivered, as well as the related commitments for financial and/or in-kind contributions of the partners will be defined ex-ante.

The 3 types of European Partnerships differ from each other in their implementation and other features. The Co-programmed are the simplest to prepare and implement, and the Institutionalised, the most complex.

The three types of European Partnerships are an evolution of certain types of partnership from Horizon 2020 to Horizon Europe, illustrated in figure 1 below.

Figure 1 - *European Partnership in a Nutshell*

The **Co-funded European Partnerships** are successors of the European Joint Programme (EJP) Co-fund and ERA-NET Co-fund actions under Horizon 2020.

The **Co-programmed European Partnerships** follow the Contractual Public-Private-Partnerships (cPPP) under Horizon 2020.

Institutionalised European Partnerships are based on Art. 187 and Art. 185 of the TFEU but are no longer called Art. 185/187 initiatives or Joint Undertakings. EIT Knowledge and Innovation Communities (EIT-KICs) are also part of Institutionalised partnerships in Horizon Europe.

¹¹ Council of the European Union (2019) Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council establishing Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, laying down its rule for participation and dissemination. Common understanding 7942/19.

Co-funded European Partnerships

Co-funded European Partnerships involve public authorities, with EU countries, research funders, and other public entities forming the core consortium. While addressing public partners at the core, industry involvement is possible without formal commitments¹².

The aim is to pool resources from EU Member States¹³ and international funding bodies to tackle key R&I issues of general and common interest, fostering collaboration and overcoming fragmentation. These partnerships result from a **Grant Agreement**¹⁴ between the Commission and the consortium of partners, resulting from a call for proposals for a programme co-fund action in the work programme of Horizon Europe.

Based on national programmes, this partnership option shows a particularly high level of flexibility in terms of activities to be implemented - directly by the national funding bodies (or governmental organisation “owning” institutional programmes), or by third parties receiving financial support (following calls for proposals launched by the consortium). The broad range of possible activities include support for networking and coordination, research, innovation, pilot actions, and innovation and market deployment actions, training and mobility actions, awareness raising and communication, dissemination and exploitation, any relevant financial support, such as grants, prizes, procurement, as well as Horizon Europe blended finance or a combination thereof.

Co-programmed European Partnerships

Co-Programmed European Partnerships, on the other hand, are collaborations between the Commission and predominantly private¹⁵ and/or public partners. These partnerships are based on a Memorandum of Understanding¹⁶ (MoU) or Contractual Arrangement, which outlines the partnership's objectives, commitments from both parties, and governance structure.

Co-Programmed Partnerships are designed to address complex challenges across diverse sectors and value chains, where actors possess varying capacities and capabilities. They may encompass one or more associations representing organizations from industry, research, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), foundations, and national research and innovation (R&I) funding bodies. International partners from Associated and non-associated third countries can also participate. Various configurations are possible, including partnerships exclusively involving private actors, public entities, or a combination of both.

¹² Programme co-fund actions provide co-funding to a programme of activities established and/or implemented by entities managing and/or funding research and innovation programmes. Therefore, this form of implementation only allows to address public partners at its core (comparable to the Article 185 initiatives below), while industry can nevertheless be addressed by the activities of the partnerships, but not make formal commitments and contributions to it. The expectation is that these entities would cover most if not all EU Member States (MS). Also ‘international’ funding bodies can participate as partners, which creates the potential for an efficient interaction with strategic international partners. Legal entities in countries that are not part of the programme co-fund consortium, are usually excluded from funding under the calls launched by the consortium. Source: European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *Impact assessment for institutionalised European partnerships under Horizon Europe*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2020. Available at: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/295096>

¹³ Member States that are partners in this partnership become the ‘owners’ of the priority and take sole responsibility for its funding. Commitments of the partners and the European Union are ensured through the Grant Agreement. Source: *ibid.* see reference 6.

¹⁴ The joint programme of activities is agreed by the partners and with the EU and typically focuses on societal grand challenges and specifically, areas of high public good where EU action will add value while reflecting national priorities and/or policies. The ultimate intent is to create the greatest possible impact by pooling and/or coordinating national programmes and policies with EU policies and investments, helping to overcome fragmentation of the public research effort. Source: *ibid.* see reference 6.

¹⁵ Private partners are typically represented by one or more industry association, which also functions as a back-office to the partnership. It allows for a high flexibility in the profile of organisation involved, objectives pursued, and/or activities implemented.

¹⁶ On 14 June 2021, [the Commission adopted Commission Decision C\(2021\)4113](#) on the approval and signature of the memoranda of understanding for 11 Co-Programmed Partnerships. You will find the approved and signed MoU for each co-programmed partnership in the partnership's Candidate details.

The primary rationale behind Co-Programmed Partnerships mirrors that of all European Partnerships: to provide a platform for "concertation," i.e. in-depth and ongoing consultation among relevant stakeholders in the European R&I system. This collaboration aims to co-develop a strategic research and innovation agenda (SRIA), typically covering the period of the next 10 years. By fostering consensus on a shared SRIA, Co-Programmed Partnerships aim to achieve several objectives:

- **De-risking of R&I investments** for private partners, offering predictability and stability in their investment decisions.
- **National policy alignment** by informing national policymakers about EU investments and facilitating coordination of national R&I efforts.

The level of additionality is possibly lower than for other partnerships. There is no expectation of a legally binding commitment from the partners to adopt an integrated approach in their individual R&I activities and it is based on 'best efforts'. However, the Union contribution to each partnership is defined for the entire duration, providing a higher degree of certainty than in other implementation modes.

The priorities for the calls, proposed by the partnership members for integration in the Framework Programme Work Programmes, are subject to further input from Member States (comitology) and Commission Services. The full implementation of the Union contribution in the Framework Programme allows for the utilization of the full range of Horizon Europe funding instruments in the related Pillar, ranging from Research and Innovation Actions (RIAs) to Coordination and Support Actions (CSAs) and including grants, prizes, and procurement.

Institutionalised European Partnerships

Institutionalised European Partnerships¹⁷ are partnerships in the field of research and innovation and represent the most complex and high-effort arrangement between the European Union, EU member states and/or industry. They are characterized by a long-term commitment and a high degree of integration based on Articles 185 or 187 TFEU and the EIT Regulation (2021-2027) for KICs. Institutionalised partnerships must be set up within the areas listed in Annex VI of the Horizon Europe regulation and will only be implemented where other parts of the Horizon Europe¹⁸ programme, including other types of partnership, would not achieve the desired objectives or expected impacts.

Unlike other partnership arrangements, Institutionalized European Partnerships are established through either a Council Regulation (Article 187) or a Decision by the European Parliament and Council (Article 185). They are implemented by dedicated structures created for that purpose. This legal basis ensures stability and predictability, but it also limits the flexibility for altering core objectives, partners, or commitments, as such changes would require legislative amendments.

EIT Knowledge and Innovation Communities (KICs) are also institutionalised partnerships relying on the EIT's separate legal base and are therefore not part of this review exercise. EIT KICs aim to address skills shortages

¹⁷ REGULATION (EU) 2021/695, **Article 11 - Review of missions and partnership areas**. By 31 December 2023, the Commission shall carry out a review of Annex VI to this Regulation as part of the overall monitoring of the Programme, including missions and Institutionalised European Partnerships established pursuant to Article 185 or 187 TFEU and present a report on the main findings to the European Parliament and to the Council. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32021R0695&qid=1705599923795>

¹⁸ Indeed, the Horizon Europe Regulation foresees that the least complex form of implementation should always be preferred, which introduces some bias against institutionalised European Partnerships that take the longest to set up. To ensure the latter, they are subject to an ex-ante impact assessment. Commission Staff Working Document. EU Missions two years on: An assessment of progress in shaping the future we want and reporting on the review of Mission Areas and areas for institutionalised partnerships based on Articles 185 and 187 TFEU. COM (2023) 457 final. Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52023SC0260&qid=1704984843316>

and are already established under Horizon 2020. Key partners in EIT KICs are higher education institutions, research organisations, companies, and other stakeholders.

The basic rationale for this type of partnership is the need for a strong integration of R&I agenda's in the private and/or public sectors in Europe to address a strategic challenge or realise an opportunity. The focus is on major long-term strategic challenges and priorities beyond the framework of a single Framework Programme where collective action – by private and/or public sectors – is necessary to achieve critical mass and address the full extent of the complexities of the ecosystem concerned.

The long-term commitment expected from the European Union and its partners is therefore much larger than for any of the other options, given the substantial higher investment in the preparation and implementation of the Partnership. As a result, this type of partnership can be selected only if other parts of the Horizon Europe programme, including other forms of European Partnerships, would not achieve the objectives or would not generate the necessary expected impacts. *The commitment for contributions (financial and/or in-kind) by the partnership members, established in accordance with Article 185 or 187 TFEU is expected to be at least equal to 50% and may reach up to 75% of the aggregated European Partnership budgetary commitments. For each such Institutionalised European Partnership, a share of the contributions from partners other than the Union will be in the form of financial contributions. For partners other than the Union and participating states, financial contributions should be aimed primarily at covering administrative costs as well as coordination and support and other non-competitive activities*¹⁹.

Institutionalised European Partnerships grant their members a high degree of autonomy in shaping/developing the strategic research agenda, annual work programs, and call topics based on a transparent and accessible process, and subject to the approval of the Commission Services. The choice of topics addressed in the (open) calls are therefore strongly aligned with the needs defined. Normally, the strategic priorities are fully covered by the annual work programmes in the partnership, even though it is in principle possible to keep certain topics for calls in the Framework Programme (FP) thus complementing the activities in the partnership. The full integration in the Framework Programme allows for the utilization of the entire range of Horizon Europe funding instruments in the related Pillar, ranging from Research and Innovation Actions (RIAs) to Coordination and Support Actions (CSAs) and including grants, prizes, and procurement.

Two forms of Institutionalised Partnerships are of direct relevance to this study, influencing the constellation of partners involved.

Institutionalised Partnerships based upon Art 185 TFEU

[Article 185 TFEU](#) (ex Article 169 TEC). In implementing the multiannual framework programme, the Union may make provision, in agreement with the Member States concerned, for participation in research and development programmes undertaken by several Member States, including participation in the structures created for the execution of those programmes.

Article 185²⁰ TFEU covers **public-public** partnerships, with participation of the EU in research and development programmes undertaken by several EU countries. This type of partnership allows the Union to participate in programmes jointly undertaken by Member States and limits therefore the scope of partners to Member States and Associated Third countries. This type of Institutionalised Partnership aims therefore at reaching the greatest

¹⁹ Regulation (EU) 2021/695 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 April 2021 establishing Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, laying down its rules for participation and dissemination, and repealing Regulations (EU) No 1290/2013 and (EU) No 1291/2013. Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32021R0695&qid=1705599923795>

²⁰ Article 185 TFEU only allows the European Union to participate in **public-public research** and development (R&D) programmes undertaken by several EU Member States. It does not allow the EU to create its own legal entities, such as JUs. Source: <https://www.era-learn.eu/partnerships-in-a-nutshell/type-of-networks/partnerships-under-horizon-2020/article-185-initiatives>, access 15th January 2024.

possible impact through the integration of national and EU funding, aligning national strategies in order to optimise the use of public resources and overcome fragmentation of the public research effort.

It brings together R&I governance bodies of most if not all EU Member States (legal requirement: at least 40% of Member States) as well as Associated Third Countries. These partners establish a dedicated legal entity, the Dedicated Implementation Structure, responsible for the partnership's implementation. Non-associated Third Countries are not typically included, but their participation may be permitted through a specific derogation in the basic act. Eligibility for participation and funding follows the rules of the Framework Programme.

Institutionalised Partnerships based upon Art 187 TFEU

[Article 187 \(ex-Article 171 TEC\)](#). The Union may set up joint undertakings or any other structure necessary for the efficient execution of Union research, technological development, and demonstration programmes.

Article 187 TFEU covers **public-private partnerships**, typically involving the EU, industrial association(s) and other partners. This type of Institutionalised Partnership aims at reaching the greatest possible impact by integrating the strategic R&I agendas of private and/or public actors and by leveraging the partners' investments in order to tackle R&I and societal challenges and/or contribute to Europe's wider competitiveness goals.

It brings together a stable set of partners committed to a more integrated approach and requires the establishment of a dedicated legal entity (Union body, Joint Undertaking) that assumes full responsibility for managing the partnership and executing the calls.

Different configurations are possible: partnerships focused on creating strategic industrial partnerships where, most often, the partner organisations are represented by one or more industry associations, or in some cases individual private partners; partnerships coordinating national ministries, public funding agencies, and governmental research organisations in the Member States and Associated Countries; or a combination of the two (the so-called tripartite model). Non-associated Third Countries are not typically included, but their participation may be permitted through a specific derogation in the basic act. Eligibility for participation and funding follows the rules of the Framework Programme.

Table 1 here below is summarizing the key differences between Article 185 and Article 187 partnerships:

Feature	Article 185 Partnerships	Article 187 Partnerships
Purpose	Cooperation among EU Member States in research and innovation (R&I). They bring together national research programmes to pool resources and expertise.	Public-private cooperation in R&I. They bring together the European Union, industry, and other partners to address specific R&I challenges.
Legal structure	Dedicated implementation structures (DIS), which is a network of national authorities responsible for coordinating the partnership.	Joint undertakings. Joint undertakings are independent legal entities that are governed by a board of directors composed of representatives of the EU, industry, and other stakeholders.
Funding	Funded by a combination of EU and national resources	Primarily funded by the EU. However, they may also receive funding from other sources, such as national governments or industry.
Examples	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EDCTP2: European and Developing Countries Clinical Trials Partnership ● EMPIR: European Metrology Programme for Innovation and Research ● PRIMA: Research and Innovation in the Mediterranean Area 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● EuroHPC JU: European High-Performance Computing Joint Undertaking ● EDCTP3: Global Health EDCTP3 Joint Undertaking ● BCE: Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking ● EU-Rail: Europe’s Rail Joint Undertaking

Table 1 - Key differences between Article 185 and Article 187 partnerships

A.1. Key features of the partnerships form

This table has been extracted from the [Impact assessment for institutionalised European partnerships under Horizon Europe](#) (2020, Appendix A, page 2178).

	Co-Programmed European Partnerships (CP)	Institutionalised European Partnerships – IP A187	Co-Funded European Partnerships (CF)	Institutionalised European Partnerships – IP A185
Partnership characteristics				
Type of partnerships	Suitable for all types of partners : private and/or public partners, including MS, foundations and international partners Different configurations possible: Industry only (current cPPPs) Mainly MS (not used under H2020, but planned for Horizon Europe) Combination	Suitable for all types of partners : private and/or public partners, including MS, regions, foundations and international partners Different configurations possible: Industry only (majority of current JUs) Mainly MS Combination (e.g. tripartite model, currently ECSEL JU, Euro HPC)	At the core national funding / research governance bodies , other partners in addition (e.g. foundations). Provide potential for more efficient interaction with strategic international partners : any ‘international’ funding body can participate independent of the country. Needs good coverage - nearly all Member States , since the topic is removed from WP.	Participation is limited to MS and Associated Countries Non associated third countries only if foreseen in the basic act and subjected to conclusion of dedicated international agreements. Needs good coverage - nearly all Member States : ambition is to propose Art 185 only for topics of common interest for all MS and if they have “a major participation” in it. The minimum condition of at least 40% of the MS is a measure introduced bearing for geographically focused partnerships, e.g. PRIMA
Form of grouping	One or more association of organisations from industry, research, NGOs etc	A dedicated legal entity – Joint Undertaking or any other structure necessary - that carries full responsibility for the implementation. In addition, for many (but not all) one or more associations of organisations from industry, research, NGOs etc	Consortium of partners coordinated by a legal entity of one of the MS or a specific representative legal entity	A dedicated legal entity – DIS or any other structure necessary - that carries full responsibility for the implementation
Key characteristics	Best suited for partnerships addressing broader communities, and where there is a need for flexibility. Partners provide input on the drafting of the respective parts of the Annual Work programme	Stable partners and substantial commitments for contributions from all partners that other forms of partnerships would not allow. Stronger commitment of partners to a more integrated approach, resulting in a higher degree of additionality and directionality <i>compared to co-programmed partnerships</i>	Best suited for partnerships that rely on pooling / coordinating national programmes and policies with Union policies and investments	Stable partners and substantial commitments for contributions from Participating States (MS & AC) that other forms of partnerships would not allow Stronger commitment of partners to a more integrated approach, resulting in a higher degree of additionality and directionality <i>compared to co-funded partnerships</i>

	Co-Programmed European Partnerships (CP)	Institutionalised European Partnerships – IP A187	Co-Funded European Partnerships (CF)	Institutionalised European Partnerships – IP A185
Strength of commitments	Commitments are not legally binding , but political/ best efforts	Legally binding commitments	Commitments are ensured through the Grant Agreement	Legally binding commitments
Strategic direction				
R&I focus	Medium term priorities	Long term challenges and priorities that tend to go beyond a single Multiannual Financial Framework	National priorities / policies Joint programme of activities agreed by partners	Long term challenges and priorities that tend to go beyond a single MFF
Main characteristics	Where the primary ambition is to generate commitment to a common strategic research agenda across a diverse set of actors / value chains and where those actors have widely differing capacities and capabilities	Major strategic challenges where collective action – by private and public sectors – is necessary to achieve critical mass on the one hand and to address the full extent of the complexities of the ecosystem on the other	Societal grand challenges and areas of high public good where EU action will add value	Major strategic challenges where collective action by public sectors is necessary to achieve critical mass on the one hand and to address the full extent of the complexities of the ecosystem on the other
Basic rationale for policy options	Concertation of industry/MS around a strategic agenda Union co-funding large enough to attract strategic investment by private and or public sectors For Industry: de-risking investments and providing predictability of investment paths For MS: inform Union investments and harmonise MS efforts.	Need for high integration Bring all relevant actors together to fund / execute all actions required to realise or overcome a strategic challenge or opportunity. Union co-funding large enough to attract strategic investment by private and or public sectors Fund inter-connected activities at an intensity / scale to make an impact at the EU level	Bring MS together to invest at scale in key R&I issues of general interest to most if not all EU MS Union co-funding large enough to attract strategic national investment	Need for high integration Bring all relevant MS together to fund / execute all actions required to realise or overcome a strategic challenge or opportunity Union co-funding large enough to attract strategic investment by private and or public sectors Fund inter-connected activities at an intensity / scale to make an impact at the EU level
Programming	Partnerships translate SRIA/Roadmap into priorities for calls – proposed to the EC for implementation in the Annual Work Programmes (AWP) Should be a transparent and accessible process □ “element of external advice” (consulting stakeholders, MS, industry)	Drafted by the partnership with a high degree of autonomy The AWP needs to be adopted by the governance body of the partnership. Should be a transparent and accessible process □ “element of external advice” (consulting stakeholders, MS, industry)	Representatives of the participating countries Negotiation process prior to launch of the call (includes negotiation on the budget - insurance of absorptive capacity among MS and willingness for co-funding) Should be a transparent and accessible process □ “element of external advice” (consulting stakeholders, MS, industry)	Representatives of the participating countries Should be a transparent and accessible process □ “element of external advice” (consulting stakeholders, MS, industry)

	Co-Programmed European Partnerships (CP)	Institutionalised European Partnerships – IP A187	Co-Funded European Partnerships (CF)	Institutionalised European Partnerships – IP A185
Coverage of topic in the Horizon Europe WP	Full integration in the Framework Programme (FP) WP	Normally priorities are fully covered by AWP of the JU, yet in principle possible to keep certain topics for calls in FP to complement WP of the partnership. There is an advantage of keeping elements in Horizon EU, but the decision will be based on the scope definition of the partnerships – and taking account of the budget	Intention is to remove that priority from the FP WP and give it to the MS for funding under their responsibility	Normally priorities are fully covered by AWP of the A185, yet in principle possible to keep certain topics for calls in FP to complement WP of the partnership. There is an advantage of keeping elements in Horizon EU, but the decision will be based on the scope definition of the partnerships – and taking account of the budget
Types of actions	Full array of HEU funding instruments typically used under the pillar, from RIAs and Innovation actions to CSAs, prizes, procurement, including specialised applications of actions (e.g. BBI Flagships) (this implies that e.g. Marie Curie actions, research infrastructure funding, EIC instruments etc will not be part of the policy mix)	Full array of Horizon Europe (HEU) funding instruments typically used under the pillar, from RIAs and Innovation actions to CSAs, prizes, procurement, including specialised applications of actions (e.g. BBI Flagships) (this implies that e.g. Marie Curie actions, research infrastructure funding, EIC instruments etc will not be part of the policy mix)	Broad range of activities that can be implemented - activities may support networking and coordination, research, innovation, pilot actions, and innovation and market deployment actions, training and mobility actions, awareness raising and communication, dissemination and exploitation, any relevant financial support, such as grants, prizes, procurement, as well as Horizon Europe blended finance or a combination thereof. Implemented by “beneficiaries” (i.e. the funding agencies) e.g. through institutional funding prog’s, or Implemented by “third parties” receiving financial support, following calls for proposals launched by the consortium	Full array of HEU funding instruments typically used under the pillar, from RIAs and Innovation actions to CSAs, prizes, procurement, including specialised applications of actions (e.g. BBI Flagships) (this implies that e.g. Marie Curie actions, research infrastructure funding, EIC instruments etc will not be part of the policy mix)
EC oversight during implementation	EC approves priorities Currently, depending on the cPPP, the influence of EC and MS can lead to the effect that the call topics and the scope are not to the same extent aligned with the roadmap and priorities of the partnership as in Art 187	EC has voting rights in the governance body approving SRRIA/roadmap and annual work programmes (typically 50% of the votes).	EC approves focus in the Grant Agreement based on the negotiation process. Approves annual work programmes	EC has no voting rights in the governance. EC decides on financing of the activities of the initiative by approving annual work programmes
MS oversight	Medium (comitology, but having to respect the contractual arrangements)	No longer once basic act is adopted except if there’s co-funding by MS (tripartite) (but: MS advisory bodies in place in all industry driven JUs)	High (MS-led) but limited to co-funding MS	High (MS-led) but limited to co-funding MS

	Co-Programmed European Partnerships (CP)	Institutionalised European Partnerships – IP A187	Co-Funded European Partnerships (CF)	Institutionalised European Partnerships – IP A185
Implementation				
Investment level	For industry partnerships: typically, in the same order of magnitude as JUs	Up to and more than 1 billion	Expected to be in the range of 50 – 300 million , can be larger	Typically hundreds of millions
Management & implementation body	EC / executive agency In future: if CP with MS: calls using national money managed by MS – EU money managed by EC services	Joint Undertakings / other structures Possibly more thematically specialised staff than in the executive agencies	By the consortium of partners in activities under their responsibility Decentralised management is the default	Usually under the responsibility of Dedicated Implementation Structure (DIS) designated by the Participating States (usually in the form of an association) with thematically specialised staff
Management of calls	Calls for proposals published in the Work Programmes of Horizon Europe	In principle, open calls (in some A187 some calls ring-fenced for JU partners which is in contradiction with the criteria of Annex III. Internal policy discussions is on whether this should be allowed)	Usually decentralised approach (only the call management is centralised) □ Cascading grant □ Multiple GAs per project consortium – with different national funding bodies □ National funding rules	By default (unless derogations in the basic act) centralised approach <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Single GA • Single set of rules (but some activities may be implemented by the DIS and some by the PS) Ambition is to have everything post-call managed by the DIS (MS don't always agree)
Eligibility for participation	FP rules apply, so fully open	FP rules apply by default, so fully open	Any 'international' funding body can participate independent of the country	Default is: participation is limited to MS and Associated Countries. Third countries can participate and provide matching contributions only if there are dedicated international agreements
Eligibility for funding	FP rules apply, so fully open	FP rules apply by default, so fully open □ also entities from non-co-funding countries have the right to apply and receive co-funding at same level as in Horizon Europe Exceptions can be foreseen in the basic act. E.g. limiting certain calls to beneficiaries from EU MS/AC for strategic reasons In cases of tripartite partnerships where PS also provide funding, the maximum funding rates of the FP cannot be exceeded.	Legal entities in countries that are not part of a CF consortium are usually excluded from receiving funding from the calls IF part of the consortium, AC and non-industrial countries can receive co-funding (similar ruling as under the FP)	FP rules apply by default, so also entities from non-co-funding countries have the right to apply and receive co-funding at the same level as in Horizon Europe. Project co-funding cannot exceed the funding rates of the FP

	Co-Programmed European Partnerships (CP)	Institutionalised European Partnerships – IP A187	Co-Funded European Partnerships (CF)	Institutionalised European Partnerships – IP A185
Integration of funding data in EC IT (participation, results)	Using EC IT system □ full integration	Using EC IT system □ full integration of participation data For results currently sometimes commercial secrecy is claimed	Need to ensure integration of a minimum set of data into EC IT systems – currently limited to data on “beneficiaries” (i.e. funding bodies), no data on “third parties”	Need to ensure integration of a minimum set of data into EC IT □ systems participation data is fully integrated
Legal base				
Legal base	Memoranda of understanding and/or contractual arrangements between the Commission and the partners	Regulation by Council after consultation of the European Parliament and the Economic and Social Committee	Grant Agreement between the Commission and the consortium of partners, resulting from a call for a programme co-fund action in the Work Programme of Horizon Europe (defacto non-competitive: integration of all relevant actors upfront) grant agreement = 5-7 years duration	Decision by European Parliament and Council
Base for EC decision-making	Partnership proposal	EC proposal based on Impact Assessment	Partnership proposal	EC proposal based on Impact Assess
Effort for preparation, setting up, and implementation	Relatively low effort for the setup and implementation	High effort for their preparation and set-up	Moderate effort for their set-up and implementation	High effort for their preparation and set-up
Co-funding arrangements				
EU contribution	Not legally defined (but similar range as IPs)	Between 25% and 50% of the total budget of the initiative, to be defined individually in the basic act Minimum ratio: 1:1	Funding rate: 30%, in justified cases up to 70% Consideration can be e.g.: Main element of financial support is to third parties □ financial contribution to calls (e.g. transnational ERA-Net calls); lower reimbursement rate Main element of activities is directly implemented by beneficiaries □ institutional programmes or specific features: higher reimbursement rate If decision for application of centralised approach □ premium (possibly higher EU funding rates)	Between 25% and 50% of the total budget of the initiative, to be defined individually in the basic act Minimum ratio: 1:1

	Co-Programmed European Partnerships (CP)	Institutionalised European Partnerships – IP A187	Co-Funded European Partnerships (CF)	Institutionalised European Partnerships – IP A185
Project co-funding rules	Horizon Europe funding rules apply by default	Horizon Europe funding rules apply by default BUT the option under discussion is for certain call topics to reduce EU funding rates for industry partners. <i>Ongoing discussion that will have to take into account possible positive and negative effects</i>	National rules and rates apply, unless otherwise agreed	Horizon Europe funding rules apply by default
Coverage of administration expenditures	Option to finance administration costs through a CSA funded under Horizon Europe - considered a 'must' for CPs led by Member States	Administrative expenditure should not be higher than 4% of the budget. Private partners are expected to contribute substantially to these costs (currently: 50%) "Taxing" of project participants to contribute in JU admin costs not acceptable under the Financial Regulation	EU contribution = partial reimbursement of eligible costs Eligible costs include the direct costs of the beneficiaries (i.e. the funding agencies) and the costs of funding projects The system implies it is up to the Member States to decide on how to distribute the EU contribution over the activities	Administrative expenditure should not be higher than 4% of the budget.
Partners contributions (beyond EU)	In-kind and/or financial contributions agreed in the work plan - typically only in-kind from private partners.	Financial but typically mainly in-kind contributions from private partners Industry partners are expected to contribute In-kind to projects In-kind in additional activities related e.g. to uptake of results	In-kind and/or financial contributions Financial contributions from Member States are typically used for calls for transnational projects. Funding for national programmes/initiatives is considered in-kind contribution	Financial contributions and, if relevant in-kind contributions Financial contributions from Member States are typically used for calls for transnational projects
Eligibility for non-EU countries				
Associated countries				
Eligibility for partner status	In principle yes, subject to policy considerations	In principle yes, subject to policy considerations (for both private partners, and where applicable, as participating state)	Yes	Yes, as participating state
Eligibility for participation in projects	Yes	By default, yes, unless derogations in the basic act or in the Annual Work Programme limit eligibility for participation	Yes, if the country participates and contributes to the call in question, or if call provisions allow for unfunded participation	By default, yes, unless derogations in the basic act or in the Annual Work Programme limit eligibility for participation

	Co-Programmed European Partnerships (CP)	Institutionalised European Partnerships – IP A187	Co-Funded European Partnerships (CF)	Institutionalised European Partnerships – IP A185
Eligibility for project funding	Yes	By default, yes, unless derogations in the basic act or in the Annual Work Programme limit eligibility for funding	Yes, if the country participates and contributes to the call-in question, or if call provisions allow for funded participation	By default, yes, unless derogations in the basic act or in the Annual Work Programme limit eligibility for funding
3rd countries (non-AC)				
Eligibility for partner status	In principle yes, subject to policy considerations	In principle yes, subject to policy considerations (for both private partners, and where applicable, as participating state, the latter being subject to international agreement)	Yes (but only receiving Union contribution if listed in Annex to WP or special provisions in call text)	By default no, only if foreseen in the basic act and subject to conclusion of international agreement (as in PRIMA)
Eligibility for participation in projects	Yes	By default, yes, unless derogations in the basic act or in the Annual Work Programme limit eligibility for participation	Yes, if the country participates and contributes to the call in question, or if call provisions allow for unfunded participation	By default yes, unless derogations in the basic act or in the Annual Work Programme limit eligibility for participation
Eligibility for project funding	Yes, if listed in Annex to WP or funded participation necessary	By default, yes, unless derogations in the basic act or in the Annual Work Programme limit eligibility for funding	Yes, if the country participates and contributes to the call in question, or if call provisions allow for funded participation	By default yes for countries listed in the Annex to the WP, unless derogations in the basic act or in the Annual Work Programme limit eligibility for funding

Table 2 - Extract from key features of the partnership forms under HE Europe

B. Selection Criteria for European Partnerships in Horizon Europe

The requirements towards the set-up of European Partnerships stem from different legal bases, in particular Horizon Europe (Art. 10²¹ (2) and Annex III). Also, additional documents include issues to be considered for the setting up of European Partnerships. These include:

- demonstrating that the European Partnership is more effective to achieve the related objectives of the Programme;
- coherence and synergies of the European Partnership within the Union R&I landscape;
- transparency and openness of the European Partnership as regards the identification of priorities and objectives in terms of expected results and impacts and as regards the involvement of partners and stakeholders from across the entire value chain, from different sectors, backgrounds and disciplines, including international ones when relevant and not interfering with European competitiveness;
- ex-ante demonstration of additionality and directionality of the European Partnership, including a common strategic vision of the purpose of the European Partnership. That vision includes in particular:
 - identification of measurable expected outcomes, results and impacts within specific timeframes, including key economic and/or societal value for the Union;
 - demonstration of expected qualitative and significant quantitative leverage effects, including a method for the measurement of key performance indicators;
 - approaches to ensure flexibility of implementation and to adjust to changing policy, societal and/or market needs, or scientific advances, to increase policy coherence between regional, national and Union level; exit-strategies and measures for phasing-out from the Programme;
- ex-ante demonstration of the partners' long-term commitment, including a minimum share of public and/or private investments;
- the political desire to enable additional joint activities beyond joint calls;
- encourage exploitation of research and innovation results and actively disseminate and exploit results, in particular for leveraging private investments and for policy development;
- strengthen international cooperation in support of Union policy objectives and international commitments;
- reinforce the link between research, innovation and, where appropriate, education, training and other policies, including complementarities with national, regional and Union research and innovation policies and activities;
- increase public awareness and acceptance, respond to demand and encourage the diffusion and uptake of new solutions by involving, where appropriate, citizens and end users in co design and co creation processes.

²¹ Article 10 - Union financial contribution. (2). The amount of the Union contribution specified in Part Two may be increased with contributions from third countries associated to Horizon Europe in line with Article 16(5) of the Horizon Europe Regulation and provided that the total amount by which the Union contribution is increased is at least matched by the contribution of members other than the Union, or their constituent or affiliated entities. Source: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32021R2085>

3. European Joint Undertakings

European [Joint Undertakings](#) (JUs) are an institutionalised public-private partnership (PPP) that represents a collaborative framework within the Horizon Europe programme to address complex research and innovation challenges. They are governed by a specific legal framework under [Article 187](#) of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU), which provides for the creation of joint undertakings "for the efficient execution of Community research, technological development and demonstration programmes." Article 187 TFEU has been used under the EU's research framework programmes to set up, in particular, public-private partnership bodies in order to integrate industrial research in specific areas.

The members of these JUs are typically the European Union (represented by the European Commission) and industry-led associations, as well as other partners. JUs adopts their own research agenda and award funding mainly on the basis of open calls for proposals.

Joint technology initiatives (JTIs) are a type of JU set up to implement part of a strategic research agenda of a broader industrial initiative arising primarily from the work of European technology platforms.

JUs have also been set up under the [Euratom Treaty](#) (Articles 45 to 51), given that they are based on the separate legal basis of the Euratom Treaty and are therefore not part of this review exercise.

[Article 45](#) (of the Euratom Treaty). Undertakings which are of fundamental importance to the development of the nuclear industry in the Community may be established as Joint Undertakings within the meaning of this Treaty, in accordance with the following Articles.

A brief explanation of the main differences between the joint undertakings set up under Article 187 of the TFEU and the joint undertakings set up under Articles 45 to 51 of the Euratom Treaty has been summarised below.

Feature	European Joint Undertaking (TFEU)	European Joint Undertaking (Euratom Treaty)
Legal basis	Article 187 TFEU	Articles 45-51 of the Euratom Treaty
Scope	Research, technological development and demonstration (RTD) in all areas of EU competence	Research, technological development and demonstration (RTD) in the field of nuclear energy
Members	European Union (represented by the European Commission), industry-led associations, and other partners	European Union (represented by the European Commission) and Member States
Funding	EU budget and contributions from members	EU budget and contributions from Member States
Decision-making	Council of the European Union, acting by qualified majority	Council of the European Union, acting by unanimity
Duration	Limited to the duration of the specific programme or project	Unlimited

Table 3 - Main differences between JUs under Article 187 and under Articles 45 to 51

European Joint Undertakings (TFEU) are set up to support research and innovation in all areas of EU competence. They are typically established in response to specific calls for proposals under the EU's research framework programmes. JUs can be either public-private partnerships (PPPs) or multi-stakeholder partnerships. PPPs are typically led by industry, while multi-stakeholder partnerships bring together a wider range of partners, including academia, research institutions, and civil society organizations. JUs has a limited duration, typically corresponding to the duration of the specific programme or project they are set up to support.

European Joint Undertakings (Euratom Treaty) are set up to support research, technological development, and demonstration (RTD) in the field of nuclear energy. They are typically established in response to specific needs identified by the European Commission or the Euratom Treaty itself. JUs are typically led by industry, with a smaller role for academia and research institutions. JUs have an unlimited duration.

Based on the "[Council Regulation \(EU\) 2021/2085 of 19 November 2021](#)" and the "[Impact assessment for institutionalised European partnerships under Horizon Europe](#)" of the European Commission, Directorate General for Research and Innovation (2020), the main insights extracted regarding JUs are:

Organizational Structure

The organization of a Joint Undertaking under Article 187 TFEU involves the participation of multiple stakeholders, including the European Union, member states, and private entities. The structure typically includes a governing board responsible for decision-making, strategic planning, and oversight. The specific organization may vary based on the objectives and nature of the Joint Undertaking, but it generally reflects a multi-stakeholder approach to ensure comprehensive representation and expertise.

Governance Models

The governance models for a JU established under Article 187 TFEU can vary, and they are often tailored to suit the specific goals and characteristics of each partnership. Possible governance models may include a centralized structure with decision-making powers concentrated in a single governing body or a more decentralized model where decision-making is distributed among various committees or working groups. The selection/choice of governance model depends on the complexity of the Joint Undertaking and the need for efficient decision-making processes.

Advantages and Disadvantages

Advantages of a Joint Undertaking under Article 187 TFEU include enhanced collaboration, pooling of resources, and access to diverse expertise. The joint efforts contribute to addressing challenges that may be beyond the scope of individual entities. However, challenges may arise in terms of coordination, alignment of interests, and potential conflicts among stakeholders. Balancing the interests of public and private entities can be complex, requiring careful governance and communication.

Advantages

- **Pooling of resources and expertise:** JUs can bring together the resources and expertise of the European Union, Member States, and industry and academia to address complex Research, technological development and demonstration (RTD) challenges.
- **Accelerated development of innovative technologies:** JUs can accelerate the development of innovative technologies by providing a dedicated funding stream and a supportive environment for collaboration.
- **Better coordination of RTD activities:** JUs can help to better coordinate RTD activities across the European Union and with its international partners.

Disadvantages

- **Complexity:** JUs can be complex and time-consuming to establish and manage.
- **Risk of conflicts of interest:** JUs may be vulnerable to conflicts of interest, as they bring together organizations with different interests.
- **Dependence on EU funding:** JUs are dependent on EU funding, which can make them vulnerable to changes in EU policy.

Risks and Opportunities

Risks associated with Joint Undertakings include the potential for delays due to consensus-building, the need for effective risk management, and the possibility of conflicting priorities among stakeholders. Opportunities lie in the ability to leverage collective resources, stimulate innovation, and achieve ambitious objectives that may not be feasible through individual efforts alone.

Relation to Framework Programme

A Joint Undertaking under Article 187 TFEU is closely related to a Framework Programme (FP), particularly Horizon Europe. It operates within the framework of the EU's research and innovation policies, contributing to the overall objectives outlined in the specific FP.

Consequences at the End of a Framework Programme

When a Framework Programme concludes, it does not automatically trigger the initiation of a new one. The continuation of a Joint Undertaking into a subsequent Framework Programme depends on its success, relevance, and the commitment of stakeholders. The conclusion of a Framework Programme does not necessarily signal the automatic creation of a new one; the decision to launch a new Framework Programme is a separate process that considers evolving priorities and the need for continued collaborative efforts.

In conclusion, a Joint Undertaking under Article 187 TFEU is a dynamic collaborative mechanism within Horizon Europe, with its organizational, governance, and operational aspects adapted to the specific goals and context of each initiative. Its success hinges on effective governance, collaboration, and the ability to balance the diverse interests of public and private stakeholders. The relationship with a Framework Programme is integral to its operation, and the continuity of Joint Undertakings may extend into subsequent Framework Programmes based on their achievements and ongoing relevance.

Bibliography

To establish this document, references [R12] to [R27] were consulted.

Appendix 3 - Analysis of specific JUs under Article 187 TFEU

A description realised in the frame of EOSC Focus project, February 2024

About Joint Undertaking set up under Article 187 TFEU.

A. Overview of European Joint Undertaking (JUs)

European [Joint Undertakings](#) (JUs) in Horizon Europe are key public-private partnerships (PPPs) addressing complex research and innovation challenges under [Article 187](#) of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU). This legal framework facilitates efficient execution of EU research programmes, primarily through partnerships between the EC, industry-led associations, and other stakeholders. JUs, adopting independent research agendas, fund projects via open calls, operating as PPPs or multi-stakeholder partnerships. These collaborations, guided by specific regulations²², support diverse EU research areas in response to framework program calls, with industry-led PPPs and multi-stakeholder partnerships aligning with program durations.

Organizational Structure. JUs under Article 187 TFEU involves multiple stakeholders, with a governing board overseeing decision-making, strategic planning, and oversight. The structure reflects a multi-stakeholder approach for comprehensive representation and expertise.

Governance Models. Governance models vary, tailored to specific goals. They may be centralized or decentralized, depending on the undertaking's complexity and the need for efficient decision-making processes.

Financial contributions. Both the EU and partners finance JUs' research activities and administrative costs.

Advantages and Disadvantages. Advantages include resource pooling, expertise utilization, and accelerated development of innovative technologies. Challenges encompass complexity in establishment and management, risk of conflicts of interest, and dependence on EU funding.

Risks and Opportunities. Risks involve delays, effective risk management, and conflicting priorities. Opportunities lie in leveraging collective resources, stimulating innovation, and achieving ambitious objectives.

Relation to Framework Programme. JUs under Article 187 TFEU align closely with FP, particularly Horizon Europe, contributing to EU's research and innovation policies.

Consequences at the End of a FP. The continuity of a JU into a subsequent FP depends on success, relevance, and stakeholder commitment. The conclusion of a FP doesn't automatically trigger a new one.

²² The main insight regarding JUs was based on the "[Council Regulation \(EU\) 2021/2085 of 19 November 2021](#)" and the "[Impact assessment for institutionalised European partnerships under Horizon Europe](#)" of the European Commission, Directorate General for Research and Innovation (2020).

B. Short presentation of three JUs

The “Joint Undertaking Chips”

The Chips Joint Undertaking ([Chips JU](#)) strengthens Europe's semiconductor leadership by pooling resources from the EU, Member States, third countries, and the private sector. Leveraging programmes like Horizon Europe and Digital Europe, [Chips JU](#) strategically bridges the gap between research, innovation, and production. This collaboration ensures the swift transfer of technologies, making Chips JU's capacities accessible to a broader research community. The objectives include supporting R&D, fostering a dynamic Union-wide ecosystem, enhancing critical infrastructures, and coordinating research programs. Chips JU's strategic approach solidifies Europe's role in semiconductor technology within a concise framework.

The “Joint Undertaking Smart Networks & Services (6GSNS) “

JU Smart Networks & Services (6GSNS) aims to facilitate and develop industrial leadership in Europe in 5G and 6G networks and services. It funds projects to shape a robust research agenda and engage a critical mass of European stakeholders for 6G-related initiatives. Primary goals include ensuring Europe's tech sovereignty in 6G and boosting 5G deployment for digital and green transitions. Detailed objectives involve enhancing technological leadership, aligning strategic roadmaps across industries, advancing European excellence in 6G, and coordinating digital programs. The focus is on strengthening digital infrastructures, preparing for future opportunities, and supporting innovation aligned with EU policies, including the European Green Deal and cybersecurity.

European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (EuroHPC)

The EuroHPC JU aims to develop, deploy, extend and maintain in the EU a world-leading federated, secure and hyper-connected supercomputing, quantum computing, service and data infrastructure ecosystem; support the development and uptake of demand-oriented and user-driven innovative and competitive supercomputing system based on a supply chain that will ensure components, technologies and knowledge limiting the risk of disruptions and the development of a wide range of applications optimised for these systems; widen the use of that supercomputing infrastructure to a large number of public and private users and support the development of key HPC skills for European science and industry.

In the following, a comparative table of the three JUs described previously will be presented (EuroHPC below due to the limited space).

Feature	JU Chips	JU Smart Networks & Services (6GSNS)
Members	<p>Public authorities: European Union (EC) and Member States (<i>Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czechia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Iceland, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, the Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden</i>).</p> <p>Private members: consisting of three industrial associations: AENEAS²³, INSIDE²⁴ and EPoSS²⁵.</p>	<p>Public authorities: European Union (EC)</p> <p>Private members: led by 6G-IA²⁶ - 6G Smart Networks and Services Industry Association (industry, research, associations, SMEs).</p>
Budget and Funding	<p>€11 billion, coming from Chips for Europe initiative (13% HE, 13% Digital Europe), 12% HE (non-initiative), 39% Participating Member States and 23% Private funding.</p>	<p>€1.8 billion (for the period 2021-27), half coming from EU (€900 million) and the other half from private members (industry), source</p>
Governance	<p>Governance board: a tripartite board, governed by representatives from the Commission, participating member states, and private members, source.</p> <p>Voting Rights: <u>It is equally distributed among the three parties</u>, except for the adoption of the work programme that has a specific distribution (see COUNCIL REGULATION amending Regulation (EU) 2021/2085, point 8)</p> <p>Private members board: SRIA</p> <p>Public authorities board contributes to SRIA; Work Programmes & calls</p> <p>The day-to-day management is overseen by the Executive Director (Prof. Jari Kinaret from Chalmers University (Göteborg))</p>	<p>Governance board: a bipartite model, governed by the Commission (2 persons) and Private members of 6G-IA (5 persons), general decision-making.</p> <p>States representatives' group (guidance for HE and other EU programmes)</p> <p>NB: <i>Member States are not Members</i> as no additional financial contributions are planned from Member States. However, they are closely associated in the governance structure. They can also become contributing partners by providing substantial in-kind contributions.</p> <p>Stakeholders group (public & private): consulted on request and is regularly informed on the activities of the JU.</p> <p>The day-to-day management is overseen by the Executive Director (Erzsébet Fitori) with the support of Programme Office</p>

²³ AENEAS is an industry association promoting RD&I in Micro- and Nanoelectronic Components & Systems to strengthen European competitiveness.

²⁴ INSIDE Industry Association is the European Technology Platform for research, design and innovation on Intelligent Digital Systems and their applications

²⁵ EPoSS is the European Association leading the development and integration of intelligent and green Smart Systems technologies and solutions for a sustainable society

²⁶ 6G-IA: brings together a global industry community of telecoms & digital actors, such as operators, manufacturers, research institutes, universities, verticals, SMEs and ICT associations

Integration of research community	Indirectly: Via events & projects; as part of industrial association and via MS mandate	Indirectly: As member of 6G-IA
Community Engagement	The community is engaged in a variety of manners: via events (often organised by the private members); via Governing board, Public Authorities Board, Private Members Board; via calls and via projects.	The community is engaged in a variety of manners: via events, via calls and via projects (3 phases): SNS JU Phase 1 (2022-2024), SNS JU Phase 2 (2025-2027) and SNS JU Phase 3 (2027-2031).
Integration of MS/AC	Part of the Governance board (decision making), but only contribution to SRIA, not main responsible	Via “States representatives’ group”, not in the decision-making body

Table 1 - Summary JU Chips and JU Smart Networks and Services

Feature	<p>Euro-HPC JU An in-depth analysis of the funding model of Euro-HPC is described in EOSC Focus deliverable D5.2 “Sustainability status and plans/issues for future work” (see [R11]).</p>
Members	<p>Public authorities (Annual report 2022 on 31/12/2022): European Union (EC) and Member States Private members: consisting of three industrial legal entities: European Technology Platform for High Performance Computing (ETP4HPC), the Big Data Value Association (BDVA) and the European Quantum Industry Consortium (QuIC)</p>
Budget and Funding	<p>Commitment appropriations: €1.374.456.640,65 Commitment appropriations: total consumption: amount (in € and percentage spent on total) Title 1: Staff– €4.699.801,29 – 52,9 % consumed Title 2: Administrative – €3.516.922,89 – 34,5% consumed Title 3: Operational – €1.366.239.916,47 – 79,3% consumed These numbers reflect the situation in January 2024. An update on budget consumption can be found in EOSC Focus deliverable D5.2 “Sustainability status and plans/issues for future work” (see [R11]).</p>
Governance	<p>Governance board: a board, governed by representatives from the Commission and participating member states, source. The Union shall hold 50 % of the voting rights. The voting rights of the Union shall be indivisible. The remaining 50 % of the voting rights shall be distributed equally among all Participating States. Some extra majority rules apply for certain articles in the Statutes. Bodies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Executive Director: Anders Dam Jensen, Executive Director, EuroHPC JU ● Governing Board ● The Industrial and Scientific Advisory Board for EUROHPC consists of ● the Research and Innovation Advisory Group (RIAG) ● the Infrastructure Advisory Group (INFRAG) <p>Governing Board: Chair on 31 December 2022: Dr Herbert Zeisel, elected in October 2021. Members: one representative of the EU and each participating States.</p>

Integration of research community	<p>The tasks of the RIAG are the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drawing up and regularly updating the draft multiannual strategic research and innovation agenda of the EuroHPC JU. This draft agenda identifies research and innovation priorities to support the development of an integrated HPC, quantum computing and data ecosystem in the European Union (EU). • Providing advice on potential international cooperation activities in research and innovation. • Issuing recommendations to promote training and education priorities for addressing key competences and the skills gap in HPC and quantum computing technologies and applications, in particular for industry. • Organising public consultations open to all public and private stakeholders having an interest in the fields of HPC and quantum computing to inform them and collect feedback.
Community Engagement	<p>The community is engaged in a variety of manners: via events; via Governing board, via calls and via projects.</p>
Integration of MS/AC	<p>Part of the Governance board (decision making)</p>

Table 2 - Summary JU EuroHPC

Analysing remarks

In the event that the adoption of the JU becomes the only alternative to be considered by the EC for EOSC, some considerations and comparisons are important, in addition to the multilevel risks.

The duration of JUs established by Article 187 TFEU is limited by construction. Their constitution is characterised by the involvement of the EU (represented by the EC), industry-led associations, and other partners (MS/AC, Academia, research institutions, and civil society organisations).

There are mainly two models of governance: bipartite or tripartite. In the first model, the EC and private members (industry-led) compose the governance board and in the tripartite model the MS/AC are also represented on the governance board.

In a bipartite model, the involvement of MS/AC is possible when the decision-making process is decentralised. Decision-making will be distributed among various committees or working groups i.e. JUs 6GSNS the MS are present in the working groups and their contributions as in-kind. In tripartite models, the MS/AC also composes the governance board. When the decision-making process is decentralised, greater flexibility is perceived, facilitating the inclusion of new members/countries in the working groups, not on the governance board. The inclusion of new members on the governance board in the tripartite model implies a new reconfiguration of JUs, which is a long and bureaucratic process. The selection/choice of governance model depends on the complexity of the JU and the need for efficient decision-making processes.

Multilevel Risks of EOSC-JU Integration

Global-Level Risks:

- Dilution of Open Science Principles: Global shift from open, collaborative research to market-driven priorities.
- Influence of Commercial Interests: Risk of commercial interests overshadowing global scientific and societal needs.

Institutional-Level Risks:

- Governance Misalignment: Potential conflict between JU's industry-led governance and EOSC's community-driven model.
- Resource Allocation Shifts: Resources may be redirected towards commercially viable projects, away from fundamental research.
- Loss of Autonomy: Research institutions might lose autonomy in setting research agendas aligned with Open Science values.

Research Community-Level Risks:

- Diminished Community Voice: Grassroots and independent research communities may have reduced influence in decision-making.
- Barrier to Innovation: Potential for a narrowed focus that limits diverse and exploratory research initiatives.
- Challenge in Maintaining Open Access: Risk of restricted access to research outputs due to commercial interests.

Individual Researcher-Level Risks:

- Limited Research Freedom: Researchers may face constraints in pursuing open-ended, curiosity-driven research.
- Career Development Concerns: Shift in funding priorities could impact career opportunities, especially for early-career researchers.

- Access to Research Infrastructure: Potential limitations on access to research infrastructure and data for those outside the JU framework.

More detailed information is available in [Appendix 2](#), dedicated to European Partnerships in Horizon Europe.

Appendix 4 - Analysis/exploration of the thematic partnerships under Horizon Europe

A description realised in the frame of EOSC Focus project, May 2024

European Partnership name	Status of EuPart	Timing of EuPart	Sort EuPart	Funding	EuPart. relevant (topic)?	EuPart relevant (governance)?	Link with Common Eur. DS?	Which EuPartnership should we liaise with?	Why and how to liaise?
Cluster 1: Health									
Innovative Health Initiative	Running	2021-2027	Institutionalised (Art 187 TFEU) – JU	TOTAL: EUR 2.4 bn - EU: up to EUR 1.2 bn - Partners commitments: EUR 1.2 bn	Perhaps for the TF Health	They had already a JU before (IMI). They might have interesting information on how the transition from one JU to the next one happens (timing, challenges, effort...).	No active role in DS Health		
Global Health EDCTP3	Running	2021-2030	Institutionalised (Art 187 TFEU) – JU	TOTAL: EUR 1.6 bn - EU: up to EUR 800 m - Partners commitments: EUR 839 m	No	No (EDCTP1 and 2 were based on Art. 185)	No active role in DS Health	X	To learn about governance models: They are now a JU, but the first 2 partnerships were based on Art. 185. So they know the pro's and con's of both models .
Transformation of Health Care Systems	Running	2023-2029	Co-funded	TOTAL: EUR 305m - EU: EUR 91 m - Partners commitments: EUR 213 m	No	No			
Risk Assessment of Chemicals	Running	2021-2027	Co-funded	TOTAL: EUR 400m - EU: EUR 200 m - Partners commitments: EUR 200 m	No	No			
ERA for Health	Running	11/2022-10/2029	Co-funded	TOTAL: EUR 110m - EU: EUR 33 m - Partners	Collaborated already (on request of ERA4Health)				

European Partnership name	Status of EuPart	Timing of EuPart	Sort EuPart	Funding	EuPart. relevant (topic)?	EuPart relevant (governance)?	Link with Common Eur. DS?	Which EuPartnership should we liaise with?	Why and how to liaise?
				commitments: EUR 77 m					
Rare Diseases	Not yet started	Start: 9/2024	Co-funded	TOTAL: EUR 50 m	No	No			
One-Health Antimicrobial Resistance	Not yet started	Start: 2025	Co-funded	TOTAL: EUR 100 m	No	No			
Personalised Medicine	Running	01/10/2023-2033	Co-funded	TOTAL: EUR 370m - EU: EUR? m - Partners commitments: EUR? m	No	No			
Pandemic Preparedness	Not yet started	after 4/2024	Co-programmed	TOTAL: EUR 2 m	No	No			
Cluster 4: Digital industry and space									
Key Digital Technologies (now Chips JU)	Running	2021-2027	Institutionalised (Art 187 TFEU) – JU	EUR 6.1bn (EC: EUR 1.8bn; Partners: EUR 4.3bn)	No	No	Relevant to Industrial & Manufacturing DS but no info found on collaboration		
Smart Networks and Services	Running	2021-2030	Institutionalised (Art 187 TFEU)	EUR 1.8bn (EC: EUR 900m; Partners: up to EUR 900m)	Possibly: SNS has developed its synergies with other Partnerships; its KPIs include a competitive data economy, and uptake of digital solutions	Yes - JU members are EC and private companies (not MS); the MS are involved through a States Representatives Group, which provides guidance. It may be interesting to study this example of a JU where the MS are not voting members.	No	X	JU members are EC and private companies (not MS); MS are involved through a States Representatives Group, which provides guidance. It may be interesting to study this example of a JU where the MS are not voting members.

European Partnership name	Status of EuPart	Timing of EuPart	Sort EuPart	Funding	EuPart. relevant (topic)?	EuPart relevant (governance)?	Link with Common Eur. DS?	Which EuPartnership should we liaise with?	Why and how to liaise?
EuroHPC	Running	2021-2027	Institutionalised (Art 187 TFEU) – JU	EUR 7.06bn (EC: EUR3.08bn; Partners: EUR3.98bn)	Yes - EuroHPC possible service provider to EOSC; possibility EOSC would be merged with EuroHPC JU	Yes - governance of relevance due to general relevance of EuroHPC to EOSC	No active role evident	X	HPC is important in the context of EOSC. We should liaise on a high (managerial) level, e.g. with the General director of EuroHPC.
Metrology	Running	Dec 2021- Dec 2031	Institutionalised (Art 185 TFEU)	EUR 687m (EC: EUR 300m; Partners EUR 387m)	No	Worth studying as the only Art 185 Partnership? Members are countries, represented by National Metrology Institutes.	The partnership is highly aware of the Green Deal and also the Digital Transformation and have relevant calls but don't obviously participate in the actual Data Spaces.	X	Article 185 partnership. Worth further study to understand its pros and cons, and possible suitability of Art 185 partnership for EOSC.
AI, Data and Robotics	Running	2021-2030	Co-programmed	EUR 2.6bn (EC: EUR 1.3bn; Partners up to EUR 1.3bn)	Not sure: focus is on applied use of data, but it may be of interest to explore common ground in AI and data (e.g. coordinated calls)	Yes - governance is similar to EOSC-A, so could be of interest to discuss experience, sustainability etc.	Nothing obvious	X	Since AI is a chapter in the SRIA 2.0. Content-wise collaboration to discuss current priorities in the AI chapter and to get input from them.

European Partnership name	Status of EuPart	Timing of EuPart	Sort EuPart	Funding	EuPart. relevant (topic)?	EuPart relevant (governance)?	Link with Common Eur. DS?	Which EuPartnership should we liaise with?	Why and how to liaise?
Photonics	Running	2021-2030	Co-programmed	EUR 680m (EC: 340m; Partners: up to EUR 340m)	No, but noteworthy that they have established a Mirror Group of national ministry representatives, resulting in joint transnational calls. This is being further built on to create new joint cross-MS calls aligned with the partnership's calls.	No	No		
Made in Europe	Running	2021-2030	Co-programmed	EUR 1.8bn (EC: up to EUR 900m; Partners: up to EUR 900m)	Probably not, although aims include uptake of AI and data analytics tools in manufacturing.	No	No		
Clean Steel Partnership	Running	2021-2030	Co-programmed	EUR 1.7bn (EC: EUR 700m; Partners: up to Eur 1bn)	No	No	No		
Processes4Planet	Running	2021-2030	Co-programmed	EUR 2.6bn (EC: up to EUR 1.3bn; partners: up to EUR 1.3bn)	No	No	No		
Globally Competitive	Officially running, but in practice	2023-2027	Co-programmed	No information available	n/a	n/a	n/a		

European Partnership name	Status of EuPart	Timing of EuPart	Sort EuPart	Funding	EuPart. relevant (topic)?	EuPart relevant (governance)?	Link with Common Eur. DS?	Which EuPartnership should we liaise with?	Why and how to liaise?
Space Systems	doesn't appear to be active								
Cluster 5: Climate, energy and mobility									
Clean Hydrogen	Running	2021-2027	Institutionalised (Art 187 TFEU) – JU	At least EUR 2 bn (EC: EUR 1 bn, Partners: EUR 1 bn) + MEUR269 (additional investment for calls)	No		No		
Clean Aviation	Running	2021-2035	Institutionalised (Art 187 TFEU) – JU	EUR 4.1 bn (EC: up to EUR 1.7 bn, Partners: at least EUR 2.4 bn)	No		No active role in Green Deal Data Space		
Single European Sky ATM Research 3	Running	2021-2031	Institutionalised (Art 187 TFEU) – JU	EUR 1.6 bn (EC: EUR 600 m, Partners: EUR 1 bn)	No		No		
Europe's Rail	Running	2021-2031	Institutionalised (Art 187 TFEU) – JU	EUR 1.2 bn (EC: EUR 600 m, Partners: EUR 600 m)	No				
Connected, Cooperative and automated Mobility	Running	2021-2030	Co-programmed	EUR 1 bn (EC: EUR 500 m, Partners: EUR 500 m)	Need to establish cooperation with: European Partnership		No		

European Partnership name	Status of EuPart	Timing of EuPart	Sort EuPart	Funding	EuPart. relevant (topic)?	EuPart relevant (governance)?	Link with Common Eur. DS?	Which EuPartnership should we liaise with?	Why and how to liaise?
					Key Digital Technologies (KDT) European Partnership for Artificial Intelligence, Data and Robotics				
Batteries: BATT4EU	Running	2021-2030	Co-programmed	EUR 1.85 bn (EC: EUR 925 m, Partners: EUR 925 m)	No	New partnership	No		
Zero-emission Water Transport	Running	2021-2030	Co-programmed	EUR 3.8 bn (EC: EUR 530 m, Partners: EUR 3.3 bn)	No	New partnership	No		
Zero-Emission Road Transport	Running	2021-2030	Co-programmed	EUR 1.23 bn (EC: EUR 615 m, Partners: EUR 900 m)	No	The governance model is very similar to the governance model adopted by EOOSC-A	No		
Built4People	Running	2021-2027		EUR 780 m (EC: EUR 380 m, Partners: EUR 400 m)	No	The governance model is very similar to the governance model adopted by EOOSC-A	No		
Clean Energy Transition	Running	2022-2027	Co-funded	EUR 791.2 m (EC: EUR 210 m, Partners: EUR 581.2 m)	No		No		
Driving Urban Transitions	Running	2022-2028	Co-funded	EUR 678 m (EC: EUR 145.448 m, Partners: EUR 532.552 m)	No		No		
Cluster 6: Food, bioeconomy, natural resources, agriculture and environment									
Circular Bio-Based Europe	Running	5/2022-2027	Institutionalised (Art 187 TFEU) – JU	TOTAL: EUR 2 bn - EU: up to EUR 1 bn - Partners	No	No	Contributing to Green Deal objectives		

European Partnership name	Status of EuPart	Timing of EuPart	Sort EuPart	Funding	EuPart. relevant (topic)?	EuPart relevant (governance)?	Link with Common Eur. DS?	Which EuPartnership should we liaise with?	Why and how to liaise?
				commitments: EUR 1 bn					
Biodiversa+	Runnning	10/2021-2030	Co-funded	TOTAL: EUR 802m - EU: EUR 165 m - Partners commitments: EUR 191 m + EUR 445 in kind	No	No	Contributing to Green Deal objectives		
Blue Economy	Runnning	2023-2030(?)	Co-funded	TOTAL: EUR 490.72 m - EU: EUR 150 m - Partners commitments: EUR 340.72 m	No	No	Contributing to Green Deal objectives		
Water4All	Runnning	6/2022-2032(?)	Co-funded	TOTAL: EUR EUR 420 m - EU: EUR 126 m - Partners commitments: EUR 294 m	No	No	No		
Animal Health and Welfare	Not yet started	2024-2031	Co-funded	TOTAL: EUR 360 m	No	No	No		
Accelerating Farming Systems Transitions	Running	2024-2031	Co-funded	?	No	No	No		
Agriculture of data	Not yet started (?)	Start 2024?	Co-funded	TOTAL: EUR 100 m	No	No	No		
Safe and Sustainable Food Systems	Not yet started	Start 2024	Co-funded	TOTAL: EUR EUR 584 m - EU: EUR 175 m - Partners commitments: EUR 409 m	No	No	No		

Table 1 - Overview of the thematic partnerships under Horizon Europe

Appendix 5 - Overview of workshop participants (Data Spaces, DSSC, INFRAEOSC projects)

In this section we give an overview of the Data Spaces²⁷, DSSC and the INFRAEOSC projects which were invited to the workshop EOSC Focus organised in Vienna in December 2024. The descriptions of the Data Spaces and the projects take into account the latest evolutions, the description of DSSC includes the collaboration with EOSC, supported by EOSC Focus.

Cultural Heritage Data Space²⁸

The Common European Data Space for cultural heritage is the EC's flagship initiative to accelerate digital transformation of Europe's cultural sector and foster the creation and reuse of digital cultural heritage content. Its deployment is funded under the DIGITAL programme. In November 2021, the Commission published the Recommendation on a Common European Data Space for cultural heritage that encourages Member States to accelerate the digitisation of cultural heritage assets, and provides guiding principles on Data Spaces for cultural heritage.

Work on deployment of the Data Space started in September 2022, building on the Europeana Digital Service Infrastructure. The initial 2-year period includes work in the following areas:

- Development and operation of the Data Space infrastructure. Collaboration with the Data Spaces Support Centre has been established.
- Data and data services: work towards a significant and sustained increase in high-quality, usable and accessible data. Using machine-learning and AI for enrichment to offer an improved user experience and new services.
- Data governance: support the sharing and facilitate the reuse of additional types of data, through new means and for new purposes.
- Strengthening the capacity and capabilities of professionals, supporting institutions in their digital transformation.
- Fostering connections with digital cultural heritage communities and with stakeholders in other sectors (cultural and creative sector, education, tourism, etc.) to create opportunities and incentives for use and reuse.
- Engaging diverse audiences by expanding pan-European themes and perspectives, inspiring use, reuse and participation.

Green Deal Data Space

The European Green Deal (EGD) recognises data as an essential enabler of the changes needed for a just and green transition of the EU economy and society. The Green Deal Data Space supports the implementation of EGD policies with relevant data (e.g. on air, water, soil quality with regard to the zero-pollution strategy) and contributes to a higher level of environmental transparency. This will result in better decision-making by public authorities and more informed and empowered citizens about their environment.

²⁷ Not all of the Data Spaces have a unique official website. For information see <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/data-spaces>

²⁸ <https://pro.europeana.eu/page/common-european-data-space-for-cultural-heritage>

European Health Data Space (EHDS)

The EHDS will enable natural persons to control their electronic health data while making it possible for researchers, innovators and policymakers to use such data in a trusted and secure way that preserves privacy.

The flagship initiative for primary use of health data is MyHealth@EU, the cross-border infrastructure for the exchange of health data, which is already operational in 12 Member States, and the majority of Member States are working to join by 2025. The data domains covered, which currently enable the exchange of ePrescriptions, eDispensations and patient summaries, are being extended to allow the exchange of medical images, laboratory results and hospital discharge reports. In addition, the services are being extended to allow patients to access their own health data.

Regarding the secondary use of health data, the Commission is financing a project to develop the HealthData@EU infrastructure and its potential use cases. The EC is also supporting the establishment of health data access bodies (HDABs) in each Member State.

In addition to this work to prepare the ground for the EHDS, there are other initiatives to improve data availability for research, innovation in healthcare. The European Federation for Cancer Images (EUCAIM) project is deploying a platform to facilitate access to cancer images and related patient data and provide a trusted framework for researchers, innovators and clinicians to develop and benchmark trustworthy AI tools based on imaging data.

Finally, the European Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI) project aims to enable secure cross border access to genomic and related clinical data in at least fifteen countries by the end of 2026. It will create unprecedented opportunities for personalised medicine.

Language Data Space (LDS)²⁹

The primary objective of this Data Space is to deploy an ecosystem that enables the seamless collection, creation, sharing and re-use of multimodal language data and models across all sectors while navigating the complex terrain of legal regulations. This initiative will empower European industry and citizens with more accurate innovative AI-based language technologies, such as automatic translation or smart assistants or chatbots, by providing the necessary data. Aligned with the European Strategy for Data, it establishes an infrastructure and marketplace while implementing robust governance frameworks specifically tailored for language data, promoting cross-sector collaborations and enhancing Europe's data economy landscape.

The Data Space will be deployed in two work strands. The first will establish an institutional Centre of Excellence for Language Technologies (CELT) to coordinate across Member States the creation and collection of multimodal language data and models. It will develop together with the Member States a multi-stakeholder data and services governance scheme. The CELT will also elaborate a blueprint for the language data ecosystem and devise the best business models for all stakeholders. Additionally, it will identify the large multimodal language models that Europe needs to develop and deploy, as well as the required datasets and data streams (e.g. public, private, citizen-collected).

²⁹ https://language-data-space.ec.europa.eu/index_en

The second strand focuses on deploying the infrastructure for multimodal language data and model collection, in cooperation with the planned Language European Digital Infrastructure Consortium (EDIC).

DSSC³⁰

Funded by the European Commission as part of the Digital Europe Programme, the DSSC aims to contribute to the creation of common Data Spaces and at the end to the digital single market for Europe to enable data reuse within and across sectors, fully respecting EU values, and supporting the European economy and society.³¹

The EOSC Association, supported by the EOSC Focus project, is in close contact with the DSSC to contribute to a common vision through the following actions:

- Monthly strategic meetings for supporting alignment of activities, sharing information and co-learning
- EOSC-A has a seat in the [DSSC Strategic Stakeholder forum](#) (SSF). The SSF is a think-and-do-tank that supports the DSSC in delivering on policy objectives. Together with the rest of the DSSC consortium partners, the SSF makes recommendations on the governance of the Support Centre’s assets, its evolution, and its sustainability. The SSF has both an active and advisory/strategic role at the DSSC.
- Members of some Horizon Europe EOSC Projects (EOSC Focus, WorldFAIR, FAIR-Impact, EOSC Beyond and FAIRCORE4EOSC) give input to the Thematic Group discussions of the DSSC on Business, Governance, Technology of Data Spaces, allowing cross-domain interactions and synergies and the creation of the Data Space Blueprint 2.0.
- Supporting and participating at each other’s events e.g. DSS2024, EOSC Symposium, EBDVF2023

Project TITAN³²

Objective:

The project TITAN focuses on an end-to-end secure data sharing and collaboration platform where advancements in network security, distributed access control, security domain segmentation, application of state-of-the-art protection for data in use, as well as usable and scalable data anonymisation are required. The work is organised in three principal areas:

- Confidential data processing enabling confidential collaborative data processing: memory encryption, confidential computing, remote attestation, confidential GPUs, confidential ML.
- Scalable data anonymisation for wide data access: Differential Privacy, k-anonymity, Secure Multiparty Computation (SMC), Multi-Party Computations (MPC), Zero-Knowledge Proof (ZK-SNARKs), and Homomorphic Secret Sharing (HSS).
- Distributed access control and transaction logging using decentralised solutions: blockchain technologies, network security domains, cloud security zones, access control and management.

Link with the Data Spaces

We want to integrate the concept of “data space connector” as part of the data sharing approach of TITAN and include privacy preserving technologies.

³⁰ dssc.eu

³¹ <https://dssc.eu/space/Mission/175308804/Mission+and+Vision>

³² <https://titan-eosc.eu/>

Identify synergies in the architecture design, components like AAI and data processing, and also the marketplace concept to registry and identification of components.

Project FAIR-IMPACT³³

Objective

FAIR-IMPACT wants to realise a FAIR EOSC by supporting the implementation of FAIR enabling practices across scientific communities and research outputs at a European, national, and institutional level.

How:

- identifying current and emerging components for enabling FAIR (practices, policies, tools & technical specifications);
- translating viable solutions, guidelines and frameworks that have been developed for one domain or research output and supporting their application in others.
- taking the next step in implementation by defining the support, governance, and coordination mechanisms required to ensure the continuous function of FAIR-enabling practices in the EOSC.

Link with the Data Spaces

FAIR-IMPACT is contributing to the DSSC thematic working groups (business, governance, technology) to (i) ensure that the deliverables (blueprint, etc.) align with the EOSC policies (interoperability, Rules of Participation, etc.), (ii) promote data quality and the FAIR principles. The Data Spaces Support Centre aims to be the facilitator regarding data space interoperability.

Project Blue Cloud 2026³⁴

Objective

Evolving Blue-Cloud as a key component of Europe’s FAIR marine digital knowledge ecosystem, providing a flagship community of practice and incubator for data analysis and modelling methods in support of applied research of the ocean, European seas, coastal and inland waters.

Contributing to the successful evolution of the (digital) marine knowledge system required to support the EU Green Deal, the EU Mission “Restore our Oceans and Waters” and the UN Agenda 2030, becoming a key link in:

- Making ocean & freshwater digital commons accessible to the wider scientific community via EOSC
- Supporting the development of analytical services and high-quality data products that add value to the core European Digital Twin of the Ocean (EU EDITO)

Link with the Data Spaces

Contribution the development of the Green Deal Data Space (GDDS)

Project EOSC Beyond³⁵

Objective

Federating Capabilities: any service to be offered in a consistent, interoperable manner across multiple federated service domains.

³³ <https://fair-impact.eu/>

³⁴ <https://blue-cloud.org/>

³⁵ <https://www.eosc-beyond.eu/>

Key Requirement: Federating capabilities communicate between <service domains> using agreed common data standards, e.g.:

- Identity management information, access/authorization tokens
- Service reliability and availability data.
- Resource usage data

Implementation Options:

- Deploy the same technology in each <service domain>
- Deploy different but compliant technologies in each <service domain>
- Consume a federated capability “as-a-service” provided by one or more providers (economics to be figured out)

Implementation Issues:

- Governance of standards
- Registry of technologies
- Support services
- Sandboxes for testing before deployment
- Compliance and certification services

Project RAISE³⁶

Objective

The RAISE project aims to provide the mechanisms for a distributed crowdsourced data processing system, moving from open data to data open for processing. To do so, RAISE will adapt open data to the culture of the research community, ensuring FAIR principles. The vision of the project is the EOSC Web of FAIR Data and Services for Science as an open, FAIR and reliable Research Community where every researcher will be accredited for their work, and all research data will be equally accessible for processing without violating data protection regulations.

Link with the Data Spaces

The project overall builds technological building blocks useful for Data Spaces. Technology development:

- Open access for processing, remote execution on researchers’ scripts (Trusted Research Environment for remote execution for sensible or data to be protected (e.g. data owner doesn’t feel confident on sharing data available for download)
- Well-structured crowdsource network of data nodes (with healthy checks for each node)
- Synthetic data generation / Anonymisation tools integration to workflows to enable shareable versions of protected data
- Research Analysis Identifier (RAI) PID to enable reproducible results of software-based analysis of sensible datasets.
- Blockchain network for registering any data access/processing and creating immutable research analysis proof (core to the RAI PID)"
- Interoperability with Data Spaces - Metadata catalogues, permission requests, data permits and data offering in SPEs, AAls, ...

³⁶ <https://raise-science.eu/>

Relevance to the EOSC

- Moving from open data to data open for processing
- Enabling open science with dataset that need to be keep protected (e.g. privacy matters)
- Attracting users with concerns (acknowledgement, pioneering discovery) of open data, moving later to open data
- RAISE technologies for other dataspace RAI ID PID: immutable proof of the performed SW research analysis (including the necessary reproducibility information)
- Dataset usage policies/contracts, dataset plagiarism checking, SW quality, security, and performance analysers.
- Overall interest: Explore the potential of aligning our system (in the future) with data space service standards (GAIA-X, IDSA, EC) or evaluate the feasibility of implementing SIMPL at RCH (main access) or RCN (data processing node).
- Interest for the EHDS: how data space approaches will serve data (as data holders) to data users for health data (Authorised Participants, HDABs, Health data intermediaries) and understand non-exclusive scenarios.

Project EOSC Focus³⁷

Objective

The objective of the task groups dedicated to European Partnerships and Data Spaces is to facilitate stimulate technical cooperation between, and organise the concertation with, the EOSC Advisory Groups and Task Forces, EOSC relevant projects, other HE Partnerships, and other relevant initiatives (sectoral Data Spaces), to ensure that relevant outcomes are identified and serve as a baseline for future developments.

Link with the Data Spaces

- Monthly strategic concertation with the DSSC on activities and mutual participation in events
- Contribute to Thematic Group discussions of the DSSC on Technology of Data Spaces allowing cross-domain interactions and synergies and the creation of the Data Space Blueprint 2.0.
- Writing progress reports and deliverable on the collaboration between the EOSC and some common European Data Spaces
- Knowledge centre for the EOSC on the Common European Data Spaces and organising events on the Data Spaces.

³⁷ <https://eosc.eu/eosc-focus-project>

Appendix 6 - Potential synergies between EOSC and other common European Data Spaces

1. Overview

This document is the result of a well-prepared workshop which was organised in Vienna in December 2024 in the frame of the EOSC Focus project where multiple stakeholders and representatives of Horizon Europe EOSC projects, Common European Data Spaces and the Data Space Support Centre were brought together. The discussion was animated by members of the EOSC Focus T3.3 team (Belnet, EGI Foundation, TU Wien and EOSC Association). The main aim was to discover common interests and opportunities between the EOSC as a Data Space for research and innovation and the other invited dataspaces. Three different areas were discussed: the first was about data sharing, protection, and security measures; the second was on Interoperability, technical infrastructure, and integration; and the third was on the use of Artificial Intelligence to support FAIR data and data quality.

2. Data sharing, data protection and security mechanisms

Data sharing, protection, and security measures are intertwined in Data Spaces and are key drivers for their effective but also trustworthy operation.

The workshop taught us that over the Data Spaces the concepts are not always clear and used or contextualised in the same way, but globally data protection and security is a priority and worry number one for all participants.

The exchange of FAIR data with or within a Data Space will only happen when trust is guaranteed by protection mechanisms. Data spaces have global information security for exchanging data in common, however in different domains and for different target audiences. There are limits to the free exchange of data products and all Data Spaces need to take into consideration:

- Data under intellectual property law
- Commercial data
- Personal data
- Secret data
- Sensitive data

The workshop discussions highlighted several key topics. These include the use of advanced security services like encryption, AI-based cybersecurity, and interoperable identity management. But most of all we are lacking clear common information and security policies all over the Data Spaces.

AREA 1: Data sharing, data protection and security mechanisms	
Terminology	Clear definitions of concepts
	Use of common vocabularies and schemas (e.g. Data Privacy Vocabulary; the DPV is a resource produced by the W3C Data Privacy Vocabularies and Controls Community Group (DPVCG) to represent information associated with processing of (personal and non-personal) data and use of technologies in a machine-readable and interoperable manner.)
Data protection and security	Protection of secure data along the complete information life cycle
	Use of common standards and policies in security
	Security by design of the Data Spaces, consent management
	Global security governance, ensuring the same level of protection over all Data Spaces
	Collecting security requirements and metrics
	Compliance with security policies, procedures, agreements and legislation, enforcement, certification, and conformity testing
	Provide services for secure data control, encryption, anonymisation, cryptography, SAML, ...
	Monitoring of the traceability and usage of the data after processing
	Implementation of global security principles:
	For each Data Space a security operation centre (SOC)
Interoperable Identity and Access Management, authentication, and authorisation	
Cybersecurity based on artificial intelligence	
Horizontal issues	Project outcomes are not necessarily just for one Data Space but can be put in common
	Training on Trusted Research Resource Environments (TRE) and security levels in all levels (from the laptop of the data users to the TRE)
	Adoption of best practices (most of the countries already have policies and best practices for securing data, do not reinvent the wheel)

Table 1 - Brainstorming results AREA 1: Data sharing, data protection and security mechanisms

3. Cross- Data Space interoperability, technical infrastructure, and integration

Interoperability is crucial for the exchange of data products across Data Spaces, involving several challenges such as the use of a system of identifiers or the adoption of common policies and standards. The evolution towards the EOSC Federation will entail an advanced degree of integration and the adoption of guidelines to ensure interoperability, the "glue" that allows EOSC to operate. The EOSC Interoperability Framework focuses on the digital object level, but its development will address services and other components ([R2]).

Key areas include the alignment and enforcement of governance frameworks, covering legal, ethical, and policy considerations, and minimising liability risks; efforts to avoid data duplication through the use of persistent identifiers (PIDs) or Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) to ensure efficient data retrieval and adherence to FAIR principles; and aligning services, with a focus on sharing available data,

publishing catalogues, enforcing access and usage policies, and providing essential services such as authentication, provenance tracking, and observability³⁸.

AREA 2: Interoperability, technical infrastructure, and integration	
Governance	Align and enforce governance frameworks (legal, ethical, policies, liability)
	Align business models
	Provide a strong value proposition: what are the benefits for a Data Space to provide service and data to another Data Space. (e.g. high value datasets/services in catalogue)
	Avoid duplicated data (e.g. use of PID infrastructure or DOI for unique retrieval of FAIR data in EOSC)
Services alignment	Services for sharing which data is made available and publishing it in a catalogue
	Specifying and enforcing access and usage policies
	Authorisation and authentication services
	Services for provenance and observability
	Facilitate the mutual recognition of services and provide mutual collaboration
Data management	Manage personal consent in a Data Space and similar situations, where the holder of the data does not equal the data subject.
	Manage data access and usage control so that the data rights owner retains direct control over their data in different Data Spaces, allowing only defined permissible actions to be performed.
	Concept of 'Interoperability by design' means that for a European public service to be interoperable, they should be designed with certain interoperability and reusability requirements in mind. The conceptual model promotes reusability as a driver for interoperability, recognising that European public services should reuse information and services that already exist and may be available from various sources inside or beyond the organisational boundaries of public administrations
	Make data tracking interoperable: data tracking is the process of collecting, identifying, and categorizing individual data points throughout the data pipeline so they can be used in data analysis. Data tracking encompasses the tools organisations use to organize their data as well as the ethical framework they use to protect user privacy and security.
	Interfacing between Data Spaces and services (e.g. machine actionable data harmonization means combining studies, experiments, file formats, or databases in an automated way. To combine them, standard parameters must be established.)
	Stimulate and implement grassroots / community-based interoperability frameworks. (e.g. Ro-Crate)

Table 2 - Brainstorming results AREA 2: Interoperability, technical infrastructure, and integration

³⁸ Observability is the ability to measure a system's current state based on the data it generates, recorded as logs, metrics, and traces. It ensures reliable operation of services, supporting researchers with a stable and transparent infrastructure.

4. Artificial Intelligence to support FAIR data and data quality

Adhering to the FAIR principles significantly enhances data quality within EOSC, benefiting AI across fields by improving model training, mitigating potential biases, and reducing data processing time for innovation.

AI can play a relevant role in supporting the research lifecycle by synchronising data formats, enhancing metadata generation to improve findability, aligning with FAIR principles, and accelerating the classification of datasets to strengthen interoperability.

By enabling automated metadata enrichment, which includes for example extracting metadata from raw data, AI facilitates cross-disciplinary access to EOSC resources. It allows researchers from different disciplines to discover, analyse, and reuse datasets beyond their specific fields.

Implementing the FAIR principles can lead to significant improvements in data management and utilisation. The potential time savings from implementing FAIR principles are significant. According to the 'Cost of not having FAIR research data' report ([R8]), applying the FAIR principles could reduce the time spent on data integration by approximately a third (28.66%). Substantial time and cost savings have been confirmed in specific sectors, such as health. For instance, the FAIR4Health project estimates a nearly 57% reduction in research time and savings of almost €16,800 per month in each organisation participating in the project, when using the FAIR4Health solution and tools (see [R9]). Additionally, making data FAIR enhances data quality, trustworthiness and interoperability, while improving efficiency in data management and reproducible AI workflows and model training. Since AI requires significant computing power, FAIRification of data helps create more sustainable pathways by streamlining processes and reducing the need for extensive preprocessing.

Regarding cross domain collaboration between Data Spaces, EOSC facilitates and maximises resource utilisation. In examining the interplay between Data Spaces and data quality, additional building blocks such as data governance and interoperability emerge as critical. This, however, requires addressing key challenges and cultivating synergies across human, technical, legal, and ethical dimensions, as highlighted in the list of topics identified during the discussion.

AREA 3: AI to support FAIR data/data quality	
Data quality	Tackle the problem of data quality in the Data Space. Excellent quality and noise reduction = good algorithms and models, reduced bias. Resolve the paradigm: elevate the quality of data for AI modelling or by AI processing.
	Guarantee the interoperability between the data quality requirements
	Use common standards and if they do not exist adopt new common standards from standardisation bodies. Data in Data Spaces should contain information about origin, provenance, representativity, data biases, trustworthy, equity (fairness), versions of AI models.
	AI models should recognise the quality and the FAIRness of data. FAIR should be the basis in all Data Spaces.
Data processing and access	Facilitate access to processing capabilities (HPC) and provide resources for processing AI services for all (not only academia)
	Metadata should contain the different transactions and enrichments by AI and assuring traceability (e.g. Is blockchain a possible technical solution)
	Interoperability between Data Spaces on verifiable data access and use policies
	Credit the original data source which has been parsed. Deal with different data sources.
	Some Data Spaces will have issues with cross border access to data and services, others not.
Strategic focus	Common business and technical strategies for like-minded Data Spaces (e.g. DS Cultural Heritage and EOSC, DS Health and EOSC, ...)
	Establish a common value proposition and funding framework to support cross domain and cross border processing.
	Common policies on legal and ethical, but also on technical and organisational policies: What is first and foremost?
	Tackle the language issue and multilingualism
	Tackle the heterogeneity of data between the Data Space
	How to reduce the ecological footprint or calculate and include the real cost of the footprint.
Cross- domain perspectives	Testing of AI models developed for one domain can be used in another domain.
	Bridging domain-specific requirements without compromising FAIRness
	Update the human factor: training and skills
	Tackle trust: how will we have confidence on the outcome of AI

Table 3 - Brainstorming results AREA 3: AI to support FAIR data/data quality

Appendix 7 - Setup of the workshop on DS 11/12/2024

Workshop preparation

The goal of the workshop was to find which **synergies** can be leveraged between EOSC (including the open science and FAIR principles applied by EOSC) and the data management strategies of thematic Data Spaces to benefit both initiatives. Since collaboration can take place in many areas, the participants rated their top 3 areas, to be chosen from the following list:

- Data sharing, protection and security mechanisms
- Policies and Governance
- Collaboration strategy and roadmap
- Technical infrastructure/interoperability and integration
- Sustainability model (incl. funding)
- Impact
- AI to support FAIR data/data quality

This resulted in an **overall top 3 of areas to be discussed:**

Area 1: Data sharing, protection, and security mechanisms

Area 2: Technical infrastructure, interoperability, and integration

Area 3: AI applications to support FAIR data and enhance data quality

Workshop execution

To foster a common understanding and facilitate collaboration, the workshop began with a concise 10-minute presentation from each participating Data Space, HE INFRAEOSC project, and the Data Space Support Centre (DSSC). These provided an overview of their initiatives and set the stage for meaningful discussions. A moderator guided the conversations, ensuring a focused exchange of ideas, while a rapporteur documented the insights for subsequent analysis.

To effectively organise and manage the workshop and discussions, a structured brainstorming technique was employed (see further below), enabling participants to collaboratively explore key challenges, identify overlapping hurdles, and propose actionable collaborations across technical, organisational, and policy dimensions. To further streamline the dialogue, three rounds of cross-cutting questions were posed during the brainstorming:

Round 1: What are the key challenges faced by the DS (including DS EOSC) and projects individually?

Round 2: Are there overlapping hurdles, and how do these differ?

Round 3: On which level (technical, organisational, policy...) do we need to find synergies in this area?

A summary of the outcomes of these discussions is presented in [section 3.2](#), with details of the brainstorming framework outlined in [Appendix 6](#).

This structured discussion format allowed for a comprehensive exploration of the topics, fostering a productive exchange of views among participants and paving the way for actionable outcomes.

Brainstorming setup

In order to tackle the 3 areas by all 20 participants, the following setup was used (see also Figure 1):

- 3 brainstorming groups were defined: 2 onsite groups and 1 hybrid group.
- 3 brainstorming rounds were carried out with a different question for each round, building on the question before (see further above).
- After each round, the discussed area moved to the next group. The next group read first the input of the former group(s), before the next brainstorming round started so that they could build on the output of the former group(s).
- Since we had to deal with a hybrid setting, the brainstorming results were noted on a flipchart as well as electronically. The onsite groups worked mainly with the flipchart, the hybrid group with the electronic document.
- After the 3rd round, each group prepared and presented a synthesis of the last area that they had brainstormed.

Figure 1: Brainstorming setup & flow, workshop on Data Spaces December 2024, Vienna